

From Triparadeisos to Ipsos: Seleukos I Nikator's Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia

PLATES 7–14

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As a result of this die study the coinage in the name of Alexander and Seleukos formerly assigned to Uncertain Mint 1 in Cappadocia, Eastern Syria, or Northern Mesopotamia is conjoined with that of Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia. The latter mint operated intermittently in the period 318–301,¹ serving the military needs of Seleukos, eventually becoming a mobile facility in support of the campaign of his army to Ipsos. It issued the first coinage to bear the name of Seleukos within a framework of the army's acclamation of his kingship.

INTRODUCTION

The foundation of this study was laid by Houghton and Lorber in *Seleucid Coins A Comprehensive Catalogue*, Part 1 (2002),² which built upon the earlier work of Newell (WSM), Price (1991) and Houghton (1991 and 1998) in seeking to unravel the complexities of the coinage of the mint operation that has come to be identified as Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia. The history behind the successive attributions

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¹ All dates in this article are BCE.

² Henceforth referred to as *Seleucid Coins* or *SC*.

of this coinage, initially to Marathus,³ an attribution carried through to Price,⁴ then to Arados,⁵ and ultimately to Babylonia, is summarized in *Seleucid Coins*.⁶

Houghton and Lorber proposed that Uncertain Mint 6A was possibly located at Opis in Babylonia, on the east bank of the River Tigris, about 70 km north of Babylon.⁷ This was a site of strong military association and strategic significance. It controlled access to Babylonia from the north via the Tigris River valley and from the northeast via the Diyala River valley. It was on the Royal Road, in control of the route east through the Zagros Mountains at the Bisitun Pass.⁸ At Opis, Cyrus the Great defeated the Babylonian army in 593, culminating in the capture of Babylon. In late 324 it was the site of encampment of Alexander's army and the army's mutiny, prior to his fateful final entry to Babylon the following year. After 308, the area adjacent to Opis, on the west bank of the Tigris, became the site of Seleukos's new foundation, Seleukeia on the Tigris; a foundation made undoubtedly with regard to the military and strategic significance of the location in the defence of Babylonia.

In many respects the operation of Uncertain Mint 6A parallels that of the satrapal workshop, Babylon II,⁹ established by Seleukos, initially as an adjunct to the Babylon Imperial Mint (Babylon I). Notwithstanding the distinctive reverse style of most of the coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A, major developments in the iconography, epigraphy and chronology of one mint can be recognized in the other. Like Uncertain Mint 6A, the coinage of Babylon II has been subject to reattribution, in this case from Arados to Babylon.¹⁰ A full interpretation of the significance of Uncertain Mint 6A requires consideration of the parallel developments in Babylon II and Babylon I. The basis for the comparative analysis in the discussion that follows includes die counts (updated as required by the author) originally documented in the studies and catalogues of Waggoner (1968), Price (1991), Houghton (1991), and Duyrat (2005).

Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia produced a single issue of gold staters, numerous tetradrachm issues and a few hemidrachm emissions. Tetradrachms dominate the output of the mint and are the subject of this die study. One result of the die study is that the coinage in the name of Alexander and Seleukos formerly attributed to Uncertain Mint 1 in Cappadocia, Eastern Syria, or Northern Mesopotamia (SC 1.1: 30–31) is conjoined with that of Uncertain Mint 6A in

3 WSM: 192–194.

4 Price 1991: 433–435.

5 Houghton 1998: 145–146.

6 SC 1.1: 3, 34–37, 479–480.

7 SC 1.1: 35.

8 Grainger 2014: 40.

9 SC 1.1: 43–50, 481–483.

10 Arados: Price 414–417 and Duyrat 2005: Groups V and VI; Babylon: SC 1.1: 43–50 and 481–483.

Babylonia. This is the latest in a sequence of reattributions that now enables the full significance of this enigmatic mint operation to be considered within the framework of Seleukos's ascent to power.

Table 1. Sequence of issues and concordance.

Series I (Philip)				
SC	Symbols	Price	WSM	Date
Ad39.1	Ⲙ Ⲁ	P165		c. 318
Ad39.2	Ⲃ Ⲁ	P164		
Ad39.3	Ⲙ Ⲁ	P162		
Ad39.4	AMPHORA Ⲁ	P163		
Ad39.5	Ⲁ	P225-226		
Ad39.6	Ⲁ :	P227		
Ad39.7	Ⲃ	P159		
Ad39.8	Ⲃ STAR	P160		
Ad39.9	K STAR	P161		c. 316
Series II (Alexander)				
SC	Symbols	Price	WSM	Date
67.1	Ⲁ	3434		c. 306
67.2a	Ⲁ Ⲁ	3435A		
67.2b	Ⲁ Ⲁ	3435		
67.3a	Ⲁ Ⲁ	3436		
67.3b	Ⲁ Ⲁ	3440		
67.4a	Ⲁ ☉	3443		
67.4b	Ⲁ Ⲁ	3444		
67.5a	Ⲁ ☉ or ☉	3441		
67.5b	Ⲁ Ⲁ or Ⲁ Ⲁ	3438		
67.5c	Ⲁ K	3439		
67.6 var.	Ⲁ	-		
67.6	PELLET Ⲁ	3450-3451	1240	c. 304

Series III (Alexander)				
SC	Symbols	Price	WSM	Date
-	Ɱ	-	-	c. 304
49.1	⊕ Ɱ	812	-	
49.2	⊕ Ɱ	-	Plate LI, A	
49.3	Ɱ Ɱ	-	Plate LI, B	
Series IV (Philip)				
SC	Symbols	Price	WSM	Date
68	Ɱ STAR	P167	1241	c. 303
Series V (Seleukos)				
SC	Symbols	Price	WSM	Date
69.3	Ɱ Σ STAR		1243	
69.2	STAR PELLETT		-	
69.1	Ɱ Ɱ		1242	
50.1	Ɱ Ɱ		-	
50.2	Ɱ Ɱ		1332	
69.4	Ɱ		1244	
69.5	Ɱ A		1245	
69.6	AΣT above Ɱ A		1246	
69.7	Ɱ over AΣT above Ɱ A		-	
50.4	Ɱ P ΔI		-	
50.3	Ɱ Ɱ ΔI		1333	c. 301

COMMENTARY

The catalogue of 251 tetradrachms of Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia is presented following the interpretation narrative. Representative coins from the catalogue are illustrated in Plates 7–14. Table 1 provides a summary of the sequence of emissions established by the die study and a concordance of the SC issues with those defined by Price (1991) and Newell (*WSM*). Table 2 summarizes the characteristics of the five die-linked series. Figure 1 summarizes the obverse die links recorded in the sequence. A summary of the previously documented die links, confirmed by this study, can be found in Houghton (1998) and *Seleucid Coins*.¹¹

11 Houghton 1998: 146; SC 1.1: 30–31, 34–37, and 479–480.

Table 2. Series summary.

Series	Date	Legend / King	Characteristics and Links
I	c. 318–316	Philip III	Rigid archaizing Zeus with parallel legs. 22 obverse dies and 57 reverse dies represented by 74 coins. Die linked to Series II via die A18. Reverse die linked to Series IV via the use of a recycled and control recut reverse die from SC Ad39.8 (Price P160). Mint control shared with Series II: K Mint control shared with Series IV and V: STAR
II	c. 306–304	Alexander III (Posthumous)	Rigid archaizing Zeus with parallel legs, plus large inverted anchor symbol in left field. 29 obverse dies and 74 reverse dies represented by 102 coins. Die linked to Series IV and V via die A50. Mint control shared with Series I: K Mint control shared with Series III and V: †P
III	c. 304–303	Alexander III (Posthumous)	Zeus with crossed legs, no anchor symbol in left field. 5 obverse dies and 6 reverse dies represented by 9 coins. Die linked to Series V via die A55. Mint control shared with Series II and V: †P Mint control shared with series V: ΛY
IV	c. 303–302	Philip III (Posthumous)	Rigid archaizing Zeus with parallel legs—recycled Series I reverse die. 1 obverse die and 1 reverse die represented by 4 coins. Die linked to Series II and V via die A50. Reverse die linked to Series I via the use of a recycled and control recut reverse die from SC Ad39.8 (Price P160). Mint control shared with Series I and V: STAR
V	c. 303–301	Seleukos I	Zeus with crossed legs. Backless throne (<i>diphros</i>) appears on the first issue and continues for many issues in Series V. 5 obverse dies and 22 reverse dies represented by 62 coins. Die linked to Series II, III and IV via dies A50 and A55. Mint control shared with Series I and IV: STAR Mint control shared with Series II and IV: †P Mint control shared with Series III: ΛY

Figure 1. Obverse die links.

Series I

Series I consists of issues in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios (SC Ad39). The coins of this series bear a rigid, archaizing portrayal of Zeus seated with parallel legs, reminiscent of the earliest coinage of Alexander III (Cat. Nos. 1–74; Pls. 7–9, 1–68). This treatment contrasts with that of the contemporary output of Babylon II in the name of Philip III (SC 481–483) that, with the exception of the earliest issues, carries a more fluid depiction of Zeus with his right leg drawn back behind the left in a cross-legged fashion.

Series I belongs to the period following Seleukos's assignment as satrap of Babylonia in 320 and prior to his flight from the province in 316/15. As discussed below in the context of the hoard data and the numismatic evidence from associated mints in Babylonia, a narrower date range of 318–316 seems most probable for the striking of Series I.

The production of Series I started using a die transferred from the mint at Arados, where it was used previously to strike an example of Price 3332 (Pl. 14, A) now in the British Museum (Hersh) Collection (BM 2002, 0101.759). Houghton and Lorber proposed that this die link “must reflect the transfer of a die, presumably to open a new mint” and that this transfer “may plausibly be associated with the movement of Seleucus from Triparadisus in Syria to Babylonia to assume his post as governor.”¹²

The numismatic evidence suggests a more specific transfer mechanism. With the reattribution by Houghton and Lorber of the Philip III emissions formerly attributed to Arados (Price P138–P158; Duyrat 2005; Group V) plus the subsequent “anchor” Alexanders (Price 3339–3364; Duyrat 2005; Group VI) to Babylon II (SC Ad41–Ad43 and SC 92–100, respectively) it becomes evident that the Arados mint was inoperative for about seventy years following the Treaty of Triparadeisos in 320. In addition to the closure of the mint at Arados, there is evidence in the numismatic record of the contemporary closure of a number of other peripheral Alexander mints at Byblos, Berytos, Damaskos, Karne, Amathos, Kition, and Paphos. It appears that the settlement reached at Triparadeisos involved the reorganization of the administration of Alexander's mints, as well as the new partitioning of his empire. Although previously unrecognized, such a reorganization and reduction of the number of mints in the East accords with the distribution of satrapies, bringing the relatively large number of mints in Syria under the short-lived administration of Laomedon more closely into line with that of other satrapies.

In this reorganization it is probable that Seleukos received official consent to establish a satrapal workshop (Babylon II) as an adjunct to the Imperial Mint at Babylon (Babylon I) to produce coinage for local needs. In one of the opening issues of Babylon II (Price P144; Duyrat 2005; Group V, Cat. No. 911,

¹² SC 1.1: 35 and 479.

D208) naming Philip III the style of at least one of the engravers that produced the Arados Alexanders that date to around 320 (Price 3332; Duyrat, 2005: Group IV, Series 11, Cat. Nos. 677–745, D162–D179) can be distinguished. The work of this same engraver appears in the later part of Series I at Uncertain Mint 6A (SC Ad39.3, Ad39.5–Ad39.9; Price P225–P227 and P159–P162) for dies A13–A17 and A19–A22. The activity of this engraver is detailed below in the section devoted to the interpretation of the die engravers represented in the coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A.¹³ From the numismatic evidence, therefore, it is inferred that some of the workers from the mint at Arados, rather than just a die, were redeployed to Babylonia after 320 in order to establish Seleukos's satrapal workshop (Babylon II).

The start of coinage at Uncertain Mint 6A using a recycled die from Arados initiated a recurrent tendency to reuse earlier dies to open later series, despite, in at least one instance, an appreciable time gap between the series. Thus Series I is linked to Series II by obverse die A18 (Pls. 8–9, 48 and 75). This die was reused after a hiatus of eight to ten years to strike the first coins of Series II. Additionally, Series I is die-linked to Series IV via a recycled reverse die from issue SC 39.8 (Price P160). The left field mint control was recut over the preexisting control that is still discernable (Pls. 9, 68 and 12, 189).

Series II

Series II was issued in the name of Alexander III (SC 67). A large inverted anchor in the reverse left field characterizes the coins of this series (Cat. Nos. 75–176). They retain the archaizing portrayal of Zeus found in Series I (Pls. 9–12, 75–176). A similar anchor symbol is be found on the contemporary issues of Babylon II, including the lion staters struck at that facility.¹⁴ Series II was struck after Seleukos had expelled Antigonos from Babylonia in 308. As discussed below, a date sometime in the period 306–304 appears most probable, with the coinage struck in preparation for the return of Seleukos's army from its eastern campaign.

Series II is linked to the preceding Series I by die A18. The reuse of this obverse die from the time of Philip III to open the coinage of Series II, at least eight years after its initial use in Series I, is not the result of expediency or happenstance, for we see the same process of reuse of Philip III obverse dies at the start of subsequent coinages of Babylon II (SC 80; Price 3339) and later at Seleukeia on the Tigris (SC 117.7b). This pattern of reuse indicates deliberate intent. We suggest that there may have been a ritual character to the reuse in order to physically link the coinage of Seleukos to that of the last Argead king, who, as demonstrated below, had particular significance in Babylonia.

Regarding the significance of the inverted anchor symbol, it is notable that the basis of power in the Hellenistic world was military prowess demonstrated by

¹³ See below, pp. 56–67.

¹⁴ SC 1.1: 44–50. For the lion staters, see Iossif and Lorber 2007.

success in war.¹⁵ The anchor insignia appears to have been placed on this coinage following Seleukos's successful navarchy for Ptolemy in the period 315–312. At this time it was probably intended as a symbol of his military prowess and success, albeit in naval warfare, that was a precursor to his military success in wresting Babylonia from Antigonos in the Babylonian War of 311–308. The anchor insignia is a reference to Seleukos as the issuing authority and its presence on the coinage of both Uncertain Mint 6A and Babylon II attests to a coherent monetary system in the province during his second satrapy.

The inverted anchor is erased from two reverse dies used at the end of Series II (Cat. Nos. 165 and 176). A parallel episode of anchor erasure is to be found on the coins of Babylon II, where the anchor is erased on coins from four emissions (SC 94.3c, 94.3d, 94.4, and 94.5). The synchronous erasure of the inverted anchor insignia from dies at two Babylonian mints indicates that the erasure was a coordinated action that foreshadowed the dropping of the anchor from all subsequent issues of Uncertain Mint 6A.

Houghton and Lorber proposed that this anchor erasure was a hostile act, associated with the presence of Antigonid forces in Babylonia in the period 311–308.¹⁶ Kritz suggested that the anchor erasure was associated with the assumption of kingship by Seleukos.¹⁷ Twenty-eight obverse dies of Series II precede the anchor erasure at Uncertain Mint 6A. At least 46 obverse tetradrachm dies precede the anchor erasure at Babylon II. To sustain the argument that the anchor erasure was a hostile act in the period 311–308 would require that the entire Uncertain Mint 6A Series II coinage and virtually all of the equivalent Babylon II output be struck early in the Babylonian War. An examination of the contemporary numismatic record at the Babylon Imperial Mint (Babylon I) and the Satrapal Mint (Babylon II), as detailed below, indicates that this cannot be the case. Rather the anchor erasure appears to be closely associated with the assumption of kingship. It may have been motivated by the desire to remove any vestige of perceived subservience to Ptolemy, whom Seleukos had served previously as navarch. This step preceded by at least five years the personal mythmaking of Seleukos, which reinstated the anchor as a personal insignia on his coinage after 300.¹⁸

Series III

Series III was struck in the name of Alexander (SC 49). With the exception of one previously unknown issue (Cat. No. 177), recorded from the commerce “Syrian” Hoard¹⁹ but misattributed at the time, this series consists of coinage previously attributed to Uncertain Mint 1 in Cappadocia, Eastern Syria, or Northern

¹⁵ Strootman 2013: 6119; Bernárdez 2009: 607.

¹⁶ SC 1.1: 43.

¹⁷ Kritz 1997: 88.

¹⁸ Bernárdez 2009: 605–606.

¹⁹ Zlotnik 2010: No. 11.

Mesopotamia (Cat. Nos. 177–185). Series III is control-linked to Series II by the new coin, although no direct die linkage is known. However, Series III is linked directly to Series V via a newly established obverse die link that involves die A55 used to strike some examples of SC 49.3 and SC 50.1. Through this die link, Series III connects indirectly to Series II and IV through other die links of SC 50.1 that involve die A50.

Series III is distinguished from preceding Alexander issues of Series II by the adoption of the conventional cross-legged portrayal of Zeus and the absence of an anchor symbol (Pl. 12, 177–185). The latter follows the convention established by the removal of this symbol from the last dies of Series II. With the exception of the single issue Series IV (SC 68), these conventions of style are retained for the remainder the mint's operation.

Series III dates early in the period 305/4–301, after Seleukos assumed the royal title—the event that appears to have prompted the removal of the anchor insignia from his coinage. Notwithstanding his alliance with Seleukos against Antigonos, Ptolemy remained a rival king and Seleukos would not have wanted to remind his subjects of his former employment by the Egyptian monarch.

Series IV

Series IV consists of a single posthumous Philip III issue (SC 68; Price P167). Obverse die-linked to Series II and V by die A50, this issue is struck from a single die pair (Cat. Nos. 186–189; Pl. 12, 189). It uses a reverse die recycled from Series I (SC Ad39.8; Price P160; Pl. 9, 68) bearing the distinctively formal and rigid portrayal of Zeus. For its reuse in Series IV, the mint control in the right field of this recycled die (left field on the coin) was recut over a preexisting control. The reverse die that was recut for this issue is not represented among the two reverse dies identified from six surviving examples of SC Ad39.8, although it is derived unequivocally from this issue. This is indicated not only by its distinctive style, but also by the original left field mint control that can be discerned beneath the newly cut control.

This late posthumous Philip III issue utilizing a recycled reverse die is a unique circumstance in the coinage of Seleukos and in early Hellenistic coinage generally. It is a result of deliberate intention, as indicated by the continuity of the eight-rayed Macedonian star mint control beneath the throne, a control that is carried into the first two of the immediately following Series V issues in the name of Seleukos (SC 69.3 and SC 69.2). Linked directly to prior issues in the name of Alexander and subsequent issues in the name of Seleukos, this small-volume emission has the hallmarks of a ritual or symbolic issue implemented in the process of the acclamation of Seleukos as king on the coinage. It complements the previously noted symbolic pattern of reuse of obverse dies from the time of Philip III to initiate Series II as well as that observed in coinage at Babylon II after Seleukos returned to Babylonia, and again later at the initiation of the mint at Seleukeia on the Tigris.

A similar ritual symbolism might be present in the initiation of Uncertain Mint 6A coinage in the name of Philip III. This utilized a die from Arados previously used to strike coins in the name of Alexander. The recurrent reuse of dies from earlier rulers, precursor mints, and/or a previous episode of minting carries a symbolic message of coherency and continuity, and even legitimacy in succession and power.

There is no discernible difference in die wear on A50 between the striking of Series IV (SC 68) and the first issue of Series V (SC 69.3) to which it is linked also by the eight-rayed Macedonian star beneath the throne of Zeus. The star was itself a potent symbol of legitimacy as noted below in the commentary on Series V. The conclusion is that Series III is contemporary with the commencement of issuance of coinage in the name of Seleukos and that it is ritually and symbolically placed in the sequence of the mint's output. For reasons detailed below this probably dates Series IV to around 304/3–302.

Series V

Series V was issued in the name of Seleukos I (SC 50 and SC 69). Linked by die A50 to Series II and IV, it follows the contemporary portrayal of Zeus adopted on Series III and maintains the convention established with the removal of the anchor insignia from the last dies of Series II (Cat. Nos. 190–251; Pls. 13–14, 192–251).

Series V opens with SC 69.3, an issue that carries controls atypical of the balance of the later emissions in the series. Of particular note is the eight-rayed Macedonian star that is present in an identical position on the last issue in the name of Philip III (SC 68), to which SC 69.3 is linked by die A50. This utilization and placement of the Macedonian star is a potent piece of symbolism, asserting the legitimacy of the Macedonian Seleukos as the successor to the last of the Argead royal line. The star appears to have held a particular significance, as evidenced by finds from the royal tombs at Vergina where it adorns the *larnax* of Philip II.²⁰ Andronikos asserts that the star is symbolic of the Argead royal family,²¹ and therefore its presence on the first coin to carry the name of Seleukos would make it an even more potent symbol of legitimacy than would reference to its more usually understood Macedonian association. This observation further emphasizes the ritual symbolic nature of the die-linked issue preceding Series IV (SC 68).

In Series V there is a newly identified obverse die link involving obverse die A50 and a number of issues of SC 69 (Uncertain Mint 6A) and SC 50.1 (formerly attributed to Uncertain Mint 1). The pattern of die wear shows that the striking of the latter was interwoven with the issues of the former (Pl. 13, 192–197 and 232). Additionally, there is a reverse die link between SC 69.1 and SC 50.1 resulting from the recutting of the left field mint control (Cat. Nos. 194–201; Pl. 13, 195–201).

²⁰ For the controversy in identifying the deceased as Philip II or Philip III and conclusive arguments in favor of Philip II, see now Musgrave *et al.* 2010.

²¹ Andronikos 1975.

Houghton and Lorber proposed locations for Uncertain Mints 6A (Opis in Babylonia) and Uncertain Mint 1 (Cappadocia, Eastern Syria or Northern Mesopotamia) that are 600–800 km apart.²² Over this distance, it is unlikely that the transfer a die pair between mints would be followed by the return of the obverse die to the original mint after a limited usage. Further indication of a single mint operation is to be found in the fact that the hand that cut the distinctively styled reverse die linking SC 69.1 and SC 50.1 also engraved the dies of a preceding Series III issue in the same style (Cat. No. 177, Pl. 12, 177), the succeeding issue of SC 50.2 (Cat. Nos. 202–203; Pl. 13, 203), and the similarly styled but multiply recut reverse die of SC 69.4–7 noted below.

The later part of Series V exhibits a degeneration in the quality of engraving of the reverse dies, accompanied by the extended use of obverse dies to advanced states of wear (Cat. Nos. 204–249; Pls. 13–14, 204–249). During this series, a reverse die bearing an incompletely erased anchor symbol was pressed into service (Pl. 13, 204–232). The anchor was partially erased and the spelling of the royal title was blundered so as to read ΒΑΣΙΛΣΩΣ. The die was modified four times during its use (SC 69.4–69.7). After the initial modification involving the anchor erasure and engraving of the legend, subsequent modifications involved the alteration of mint controls. This multiply reengraved die bears a depiction of Zeus in a cross-legged posture, which excludes the possibility that it represents the reuse of an old Series II die. The original underlying reverse was engraved by the same hand as that which engraved the reverse die that was recut and shared between SC 69.1 and SC 50.1. It is likely that the underlying reverse die was engraved immediately following the decision to remove the anchor from all Seleukos's coinage and to replace the archaizing portrayal of Zeus. An error, resulting from habit, may have led the engraver to cut the anchor on the new style reverse die. The incomplete die was then put aside, only to be recut and finished at a later date by a less-skilled hand. The blundered spelling of the royal title, the lack of care with which the anchor was incompletely erased from the die, plus the crudely recut controls are consistent with this explanation. The continued use and recutting of controls on such a substandard reverse die most probably indicate a lack of experienced or skilled engravers at the mint during this period of its operation. The four different control states of this repeatedly recut reverse die may represent either a short period of rapidly changing demands for small amounts of coinage under different administrative controls, or alternatively, a more protracted period of mint operation, during which small amounts of coinage were struck intermittently, each under different administrative controls and all within the life of a single reverse die (i.e., 5,000–10,000 coins in total over four separate occasions).

The degeneration in the quality of dies in Series V suggests a mint starved for skilled engravers—a situation not in evidence at any time in the preceding history of

22 SC 1.1: 30 and 35.

the mint. The circumstances of the mint must have changed in the course of striking Series V. This is further emphasized by the fact that the relatively poor quality of this mintage is reversed in the final coins of Series V (Cat. Nos. 250–251; Pl. 14, 251). These were struck from a single high-quality, unworn obverse die, and two reverse dies with a good quality of engraving. These final dies originated from the hand of an engraver not seen previously in the mint's operation. These observations are consistent with the evolution of the mint from a static facility at Opis with access to skilled engravers, into a mobile operation largely remote from the latter. The context for this development will be outlined in the interpretation of the significance of the mint.²³

Series V dates to the period after the assumption of the royal title by Seleukos. Placed in the historical context, these coins must fall into the brief period following the eastern *anabasis* of Seleukos, but prior to his confrontation with Antigonos at Ipsos (i.e., 304/3–301). This interpretation is further developed in the following discussion.

STATISTICS AND ESTIMATED SIZE OF ISSUES

Fifty-eight obverse dies and 160 reverse dies are documented in the catalogue. Based on the statistical methodology of Esty (2006), an estimated 78 dies were used in the mint (Table 3a, below). Assuming an average obverse die life of 20,000 coins,²⁴ with coins struck at the Attic weight standard of 17.2 g per coin (close to the observed modal weight of 17.1 g in the catalogue), this would represent a total coinage of approximately 1,030 Attic talents, or approximately 27 metric tons of silver, making this one of the more significant mint operations under the direct control of Seleukos before 301.

The overall statistical coverage of the mint's output is high ($C_{est} = 0.90$) with a narrow range of uncertainty at the 95% confidence level (± 8 dies) attached to the estimated number of dies used at the mint. However, on a series by series basis the statistical coverage is not uniform (Table 3b, below). The highest coverage ($C_{est} = 1.0$) and apparent survival rate ($n/d = 12.4$) is to be found in Series V. Coverage is lowest for Series III ($C_{est} = 0.67$) for which relatively few specimens have survived ($n/d = 1.8$), to the extent that considerable uncertainty attaches to the estimated number of dies used to strike this series.

²³ See below, p. 74.

²⁴ Callataÿ 2011.

Table 3a. Estimated dies for the total output of Mint 6A.

Sample size (<i>n</i>)	251
Obverse dies (<i>d</i>)	58
Singletons (<i>d</i> ₁)	25
<i>n/d</i>	4.33
Coverage (<i>Cest</i>)	0.90
Estimated Dies (<i>Dest</i>)	78.3
95% Confidence Interval	70.8–86.5

Table 3b. Estimated dies of Mint 6A by Series.

Series	I	II	III	IV	V
Sample size (<i>n</i>)	74	102	9	4	62
Obverse dies (<i>d</i>) *	22	28 (+1)	5	0 (+1)	3 (+2)
Singletons (<i>d</i> ₁)	9	13	3	0	0
<i>n/d</i>	3.4	3.5	1.8	4.0	12.4
<i>Cest</i>	0.88	0.87	0.67	1.0	1.0
<i>Dest</i> **	30	40	10	1	3
95% Confidence Interval	24.5–37.2	33.3–47.0	4.9–24.0	0.5–2.0	2.8–3.3
Approx. Talents Coined **	397	529	132	13	40

*Only new obverse dies counted in each series. Dies carried over from prior series indicated in parentheses.

**Cumulative *Dest* calculated on an individual series basis is 5% greater than that determined on the basis of the statistics of the total catalogue, but falls within the 95% Confidence Interval. Similarly this approach results in a marginally higher estimate of cumulative talents coined than that derived from the *Dest* of the total catalogue.

METROLOGY

The distribution of weights recorded for 239 coins in the catalogue has a strongly developed mode around 17.1 g (Fig. 2, below). Although the distribution of the total catalogue of weights appears to conform closely to that expected for a mint striking coinage on the Attic weight standard, an analysis of the distribution of coin weights by series shows a 1 percent reduction in modal weight from Series I (17.18 g) to Series V (17.02 g) (Table 4). Iossif and Lorber noted an identical weight reduction in the lion staters struck during the second satrapy of Seleukos compared to the pre-Seleukid issues.²⁵ Taken together with the observed weight reduction established in his Alexandrine coinage at Uncertain Mint 6A, it appears

25 Iossif and Lorber 2007: 351.

that Seleukos pursued a deliberate policy of subtle weight reduction in the Babylonian coinage struck during his second satrapy.

Table 4. Metrology of each series.

Weight (g)	Series I	Series II	Series III	Series IV	Series V	Total
17.35–17.39		2			1	3
17.30–17.34	4	2				6
17.25–17.29	3	5	1			9
17.20–17.24	9	6			1	16
17.15–17.19	8	9			5	22
17.10–17.14	10	9	1	1	4	25
17.05–17.09	4	16	1	1	5	27
17.00–17.04	6	5	2		7	20
16.95–16.99	2	4	1		6	13
16.90–16.94	4	5			6	15
16.85–16.89	3	4	1		2	10
16.80–16.84	2	4			7	13
16.75–16.79	1	4	1	1	1	8
16.70–16.74	2	6			2	10
16.65–16.69		1			2	3
16.60–16.64	2					2
16.55–16.59		4			2	6
16.50–16.54	1				2	3
16.45–16.49	2	1	1			4
16.40–16.44	1	1				2
16.35–16.39	2			1		3
16.30–16.34			1			1
16.25–16.29		1				1
16.20–16.24		1				1
16.15–16.19	1	2				3
16.10–16.14	1	1				2
16.05–16.09		1				1
16.00–16.04		1				1
< 16.00	4	3	1		1	9

Figure 2. Metrology.

DIE ENGRAVERS

The work of 12 engravers can be identified in the 58 obverse dies documented in the catalogue (Table 5). In a general sense the distribution of engravers is consistent with three discrete phases of operation of the mint corresponding to Series I, Series II, and Series III–V. Four engravers (4, 6, 8, and 10) were responsible for 70% of the obverse dies used over the life of the mint. Excluding the extended use of die A50 in later series, the contribution of the first three of these prolific engravers is limited to Series I and II. The fourth engraver (10) was responsible for 62% of the new dies commissioned for Series III–V. Discounting dies carried over for use in later series, only in two instances can the handiwork of engravers from a prior series be recognized in the new dies of a later series; engraver 4 responsible for dies in Series I and II and engraver 10 responsible for dies in Series III and V.

Die A1 was engraved at Arados. It appears that the engraver of this die did not accompany the transfer of the die to Babylonia for his work is not recognized in the mint's subsequent output, or in that of the contemporary coinage of Babylon II. Five engravers were responsible for the balance of Series I dies (A2–A22), with one engraver (6) producing 40% of the dies in Series I. The work of this engraver forms a tightly die-linked series. The consistently evolving obverse style (dies A13–A17 and A19–A22) is distinctively different from that of the earlier dies of Series I and sufficient to suggest that this represents a continuous episode in the operation of the mint. The work of engraver 6 is recognized in the opening issues of Babylon II (Price P144, SC Ad 43.4; cf. Pl. 14, B) and in many of the coins of Arados (Price 3332; cf. Duyrat, 2005: Group IV, Series 11, nos. 677–745, D162–D179) to the

extent that it can be stated confidently that this engraver was transferred from Arados to Babylonia in the wake of the settlement of Triparadeisos.

Table 5. Die engravers.

Engraver	Obverse Die Number	Series
1	1 (die transferred from Arados)	I
2	2, 3, 4	I
3	5, 6, 7	I
4	8, 18, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 32, 33	I and II
5	9, 10, 11, 12	I
6	13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22	I
7	30, 31, 34	II
8	35, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50	II, IV, and V
9	51	III
10	52, 53, 54, 55, 56	III and V
11	57	V
12	58	V

Only one engraver (4) of Series I is represented in Series II, for which he produced one third of the dies, including the die (A18) linking the two series. In the later part of Series II, another highly productive engraver (8) appears. This individual was responsible for about half of the Series II dies, including die A50 that links to Series IV and V.

The five new obverse dies (A51–A55) put into use during Series III are from two engravers (9 and 10) previously unseen in the mint's output. The second of these engravers (10) engraved A56, which was introduced early in Series V. Two additional dies (A57 and A58) appear in the later part of Series V, produced by another two engravers not seen before. The dies are very different in style than those seen previously.

PATTERN OF DIE USE

The average reverse/obverse (P/A) die ratio for the mint's total output is 2.8. During Series V the ratio increases to a maximum of 4.4 (Table 6, below). The higher ratio observed in Series V is associated with the use of a few obverse dies to very high states of wear, previously unseen in the mint's operation. This is accompanied by the noted degeneracy in the engraving of the reverse dies, suggestive of changes to the mint operation in the closing stage of Series V.

Table 6. Die pairing ratios.

Series	I	II	III	IV	V
A dies*	22	29	5	1	5
P dies	57	74	6	1	22
P/A	2.59	2.55	1.2	1.0	4.4

*Total obverse die count exceeds 58 dies due to four dies shared between the various series.

For the most part, Series I and II were each struck in a linear fashion. However, the development of die breaks on A50 indicates that SC 67.5c was struck in a manner that was interwoven with SC 67.6 while the synchronous erasure of the anchor from the final reverse dies of SC 67.5c (Cat. No. 165) and SC 67.6 (Cat. No. 176) indicates that the final components of these issues using obverse dies A49 and A50 were struck in parallel. This is the only clear physical evidence of parallel striking in the Uncertain Mint 6A sequence. It is suggestive of a period of high demand for the mint's coinage. In the historical context this is associated most plausibly with the return of the army from its eastern *anabasis* in 304/3 and the ensuing settlement of accounts.

Throughout Series I and II, dies were replaced after moderate wear or breakage. The replacement dies were of consistently good style, suggesting that skilled engravers were available to make new dies, as and when required. Series III dies are of a consistently high standard, although notably from the hands of two engravers not previously seen in the earlier series. The new suite of mint controls following the first issue of Series III, plus the new reverse style of the series, indicates a new phase of operation of the mint commencing with Series III.

Series IV involves a recycled and recut reverse die from Series I, coupled with an obverse die (A50) from the last of Series II and the first of Series V, which effectively links the coinage of Seleukos to that of his immediate predecessor, the last of the Argead line, in a symbolic statement of legitimacy. This recycling of dies is the result of deliberate choice associated with a ritual pattern of issuance of small coinages in the name of Philip III, on significant occasions, as discussed previously.

Series V is notable for the fact that two obverse dies (A50 and A55) carried over from the prior Series II, III, and IV continued in use for most of this final series, while three new obverse dies (A56, A57, and A58) were introduced. The last two dies are from engravers not previously seen at the mint. During Series V, 22 new reverse dies, often crudely engraved and frequently recut were put into use, while the two carried-over obverse dies were pushed to levels of wear never before seen at the mint. This is responsible for the observed increase in the reverse/obverse die ratio. Introduced into the sequence at this time was the penultimate obverse die (A57) that is stylistically dissimilar to any other in the catalogue. It can only represent an engraver temporarily seconded to the mint for a single die, or a die borrowed from another facility.

In the late stage of Series V, the reverse dies are either of problematic origin, showing multiple episodes of crude recutting (four reverse dies) accompanied by a blundered spelling of the royal title, or they are cut in a manner characterized by a consistent but degenerate style on eight successive reverse dies. These late Series V reverse dies appear to be the product of a semi-skilled engraver (Pl. 14, 233–249), a contrast to the situation that prevailed previously in the mint's operation.

For the final issue of Series V a new obverse (A58) plus two reverse dies in moderately good style were put into service (Pl. 14, 251). These dies are from a skilled engraver not seen before in the series. With these dies the final output of the mint was struck.

The changing pattern of die use observed in Series III–IV, occurring within the life of two obverse dies A50 and A55, suggests that an engraving resource constraint emerged quite abruptly in the mint. In the final period of the mint's operation there appear to have been two occasions (dies A57 and A58) in which the mint had opportunity to either temporarily draw upon skilled resources, or obtain obverse dies from the inventory of another mint.

The interpretation of the closure of the mint at the end of Series V respects and maintains the *Seleucid Coins* attribution of SC 51–54 to Uncertain Mint 1. These issues comprise a small die-linked series in the name of Antiochus I that show little stylistic affinity, or die linkage to the SC 49 and SC 50 emissions now attributed to Uncertain Mint 6A. They postdate the latter by at least seven years if considered to be coregency issues, or at least two decades if attributed to the sole reign of Antiochus I.

SYMBOLS AND CONTROLS

Thirty-three different symbols, monograms and letter controls appear on the tetradrachms in the catalogue of Uncertain Mint 6A (Table 1, above). Of these mint controls only four recur in more than one series. At least half of the total are to be found also on the coinage of Seleukos from other mints during his reign. Twelve are represented the coinage of Babylon I and II struck during the period 318–301, while seven are represented on the subsequent issues from Seleukeia on the Tigris (Table 7, below). The recurrence of nine controls on the contemporary coinage of Babylon II, including the lion stater issues, suggests a close administrative association with Uncertain Mint 6A.

Table 7. Recurrent mint controls.

Uncertain Mint 6A Symbol	Babylon II Lion Staters	Babylon II	Babylon I	Seleukeia on Tigris
K				X
:		X		
STAR		X		
ANCHOR	X	X		X
⌘	X		X	X
⌘			X	X
·		X		
⌘		X		
Σ				X
⌘	X	X		
⌘		X		
A	X		X	X
⌘	X	X		
ΔI	X			X

The wreath control control on SC 67.5a is an attempt to replicate the control of the prior Antigonid issues of Babylon I. On SC 67.5a, the central monogram is framed by a diadem, the symbol of kingship in the Hellenistic world, rather than a wreath. Moreover, the control is always located beneath the throne of Zeus and not in the left field of the reverse. It is tempting to relate this issue, a component of the largest emission from the mint, directly to the moment that Seleukos took the royal title. Support for this speculation may be found in the only gold stater issue (SC 66) struck by the mint. It bears the same control monograms as that of the tetradrachm issue SC 67.5b, including the E^{P} control shared with SC 67.5a. The assumption of kingship would have been a fitting occasion and incentive for a gold issue in what was otherwise a totally silver coinage at Uncertain Mint 6A. That the gold stater issue and the diademed monogram are associated with the largest tetradrachm emission from the mint, derived from 18 dies, attests to a significant event. It is

notable that a parallel issue of gold staters (SC 93) from Babylon II is associated by controls with the late “anchor” Alexander series (SC 94.4–6) of that mint. The apparently synchronous gold stater issues towards the end of the “anchor” series at both mints points to an event of importance. A celebration of the assumption of kingship by Seleukos would appear to be the most plausible motivation for these issues, even though the royal title had yet to appear on his coinage.

HOARDS

Table 7 (below) summarizes the hoard record for the coins of Uncertain Mint 6A including those now reattributed from Uncertain Mint 1. Additionally, the presence of associated issues of Babylon I and II is noted in each hoard.

The find locations of Series I and II overlap over a wide area including Babylonia and the East, as well as Europe and Asia Minor through Syria to Egypt. In contrast, those of Series III–V show a more limited geographic distribution, almost exclusively restricted to Asia Minor. In a general sense these distributions are consistent with the documented redeployment of Macedonian veterans and/or movements of Seleukos and/or his army at various times in the period 320–301.

Series I was struck prior to flight of Seleukos and his companions to Egypt in 316/15 BC. This took a route through Mesopotamia and Syria and thence into Egypt.²⁶ The flight of Seleukos may have provided the mechanism by which some of the Series I coinage was introduced into these regions. Following the departure of Seleukos, Antigonos took control of the troops in Babylon. Associated troop redeployments over the following three years could have resulted in further dispersal of the Series I coinage into Syria and Asia Minor.

The find locations of Series II show a primary concentration (37 coins) in Asia Minor with a secondary concentration (13 coins) in Babylonia and the East. After 304/3, Seleukos's attention turned west, culminating in the deployment of his army to Asia Minor for the decisive encounter with Antigonos at Ipsos. The introduction of Series II coinage into Asia Minor is likely to have been associated with this military campaign, which would also explain the find locations of Series III, IV, and V coinage. The latter are almost exclusively found in Asia Minor, with the data dominated by two hoards, Ankara (*IGCH* 1399) and “Seleucus I” (*CH* 10.265).

The only Syrian finds including the coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A Series II, III, and V is that of the Commerce “Syria” Hoard documented by Zlotnik (2010) who went so far as to conclude that the hoard provides evidence that the “Babylon” Alexanders that constitute 37 percent of the hoard are perhaps better attributed to an unknown mint in Syria. This conclusion takes no account of the division of Antigonos's domain following his defeat at Ipsos in 301, which saw Seleukos embark on a massive program of city-building in Syria, accompanied by extensive sponsored immigration of Greek settlers in the early years of the third century.²⁷

²⁶ Grainger 1990: 53–55.

²⁷ Grainger 2014: 82–100.

By this means it is likely that much of the Babylonian content of the hoard, including the coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A, was introduced into Syria, possibly with redeployed Seleukid military, or Greek settlers moving from Babylonia.

The range of closure dates for different hoards is consistent with the dating of the mint's output to the two decades prior to 300. Notably the hoard data provides indirect evidence for the dating of the start of Series I to c. 318. The earliest issues of Uncertain Mint 6A (and Babylon II) in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios are absent from the Demanhur Hoard (*IGCH* 1664) in contrast to the abundant presence in the hoard of these types down to and including the penultimate "wheel" issue in the name of Philip III (Price P200) issued from Babylon I. This dichotomy in the presence of Babylonian issues in the name of Philip III suggests that the earliest output of Uncertain Mint 6A (Series I) cannot significantly predate the closure of the Demanhur Hoard in 318 BC. Indirect support for this view is to be found in the fact that the obverse die used to initiate the coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A originally derived from Arados where it was used to strike an issue of Price 3332, the last of the Aradian issues present in the Demanhur Hoard.

Series II coins are absent from the coin hoards that closed around 305 (Table 8) despite the presence in these hoards of Series I coins accompanied by abundant Imperial Mint (Babylon I) coins dating as late as 308.²⁸ This suggests that Series II issues do not date to the earliest years of the second satrapy of Seleukos as proposed by Houghton and Lorber,²⁹ but rather postdate the Babylonian War (311–308). Series II–V are present in hoards dating to the earliest years of the third century, which, taken together with their absence in hoards to 305 indicates that these issues were struck in the closing years of the fourth century.

HISTORICAL FRAMEWORK AND CHRONOLOGY

Uncertain Mint 6A was one of three primary facilities in Babylonia that produced coinage under Seleukos prior to 305, the others being Babylon I and Babylon II as detailed by Houghton and Lorber.³⁰ Like Babylon II, Uncertain Mint 6A commenced operation during the first Babylonian satrapy of Seleukos I, and produced coinage solely in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios (Series I). Measured by both number of issues and number of obverse dies, Uncertain Mint 6A was the third most prolific mint in the Macedonian empire to produce tetradrachms in the name of Philip III (Table 9, below, and Fig. 3). Only Babylon I and Babylon II exceeded its output. The total output of the three Babylonian mints in the name of Philip III accounted for around 80 percent of all tetradrachm production in the Macedonian empire in the name of that king. This large Babylonian production was undertaken during Philip's reign to the complete exclusion of issues in the name of Alexander in contrast to other mints of the time.

²⁸ Waggoner 1968: 187–188.

²⁹ *SC* 1.1: 34–35.

³⁰ *SC* 1.1: 34–48.

Table 8. Hoards.

Hoard	Date	Series I	Series II	Series III	Series IV	Series V	Babylon I	Babylon II
East:								
Mesopotamia or Babylonia 1954 (<i>IGCH</i> 1751)	305–300	1	1				3	1
Mosul (<i>IGCH</i> 1758)	c. 300		1				1	2
Haynes Babylonia (<i>IGCH</i> 1761)	c. 280	2	1				20	14
Qazvin (<i>IGCH</i> 1796)	c. 280		5				4	5
Failaka (<i>CH</i> 8.256 and 10.264)	c. 285	1	1				3	-
Pasargadae I (<i>ICGH</i> 1795)	c. 280	1	1				1	1
Mashtal (<i>CH</i> 4.33)	c. 260		2				+	2
Quetta (<i>CH</i> 10.275)	206–200		1				3	2
Syria and Levant:								
Aleppo 1893 (<i>IGCH</i> 1516)	307–305	1					275	1
Jericho (<i>CH</i> 8.215)	c. 305	1					6	1
Syria 2010 (<i>INR</i> 5)	300–295	2	1	1		1	27	-
Egypt:								
Kuft (<i>IGCH</i> 1670)	c. 305	1					54	2
Phacous (<i>IGCH</i> 1678)	c. 305	4					141	6
Egypt 1894 (<i>IGCH</i> 1670)	c. 305	1					8	-

Hoard	Date	Series I	Series II	Series III	Series IV	Series V	Babylon I	Babylon II
Asia Minor:								
Asia Minor 1989 (CH 8.236)	c. 300		2				1	
Asia Minor 1970 (CH 1. 55)	c. 293/2	2	1				166	-
Ankara (IGCH 1399)	c. 290	9	3	2	3	22	29	8
Mersin (ICGH 1424)	c. 285	1					9	2
"Seleucus I" (CH 10.265)	c. 281	5	18			4	161	58
Turkey 1973/4								
(CH 1.56)	c. 275	3					1	5
Armenak (IGCH 1423)	275-270	2					57	7
Meydancikkale								
(CH 7.8 and 8.308)	c. 240	10	9		1		252	32
Kirazli (IGCH 1369)	c. 230	2	2				27	9
Gordion 1951 (IGCH 1406)	c. 210	2	2				1	-
Europe:								
Prilepec (IGCH 448)	c. 280	2	3				24	3
Zemun (Serbia) 1924 (IGCH 458)	c. 220		1				7	1

Table 9. Tetradrachm issues in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios.

Mint	Price Numbers	Number of Emissions	Obverse Dies	In Demanhur Hoard
Pella	P1	1	2	Yes
Uncertain Greece	P7–P8	2	2	No
Sardis	P98, P105, P109	3	4	No
Side	P119–P121 P125A	3	4	Yes
Salamis	P129, P130	2	5	Yes
Myriandros	P133, P134, P136, P137	4	1	Yes
Sidon	P169, P175, P177, P– (year 17 equivalent of Price 3502)	4	6	Yes
Babylon I	P181–P184, P186, P189, P190, P192, P194, P197, P200, P202, P205, P206	14	71	Yes
Babylon II (Arados of Price and Duyrat)	P139, P141, P142, P144, P147, P148, P150–153, P155, P156, P158	13	68	No
Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Marathus plus some Uncertain East of Price)	P159, P160, P161, P162, P163, P164, P165, P225, P226, P227	10	22	No
Susa	P208, P212–P218	8	9	No
Ekbatana (?)	P221	1	1	No
Uncertain	P229, P233, P237, P238	4	5	No
Posthumous Issues:				
Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Marathus of Price)	P167	1	1	No

When compared to other parts of the Macedonian empire, the numismatic data indicate that Philip III Arrhidaios held a particular significance in Babylonia under Seleukos as satrap. Following the death of Alexander the Great, the assembled Macedonian infantry in Babylon sought to acclaim Phillip III Arrhidaios as king and successor to Alexander, in conflict with the Companion Cavalry who preferred the not-yet-born Alexander IV. The acclamation of the pure-blood member of the Argead royal line by the infantry veterans in Babylon was the only one formally recognized on the coinage of Babylonia in the six years following the death of

Figure 3. Philip III tetradrachm obverse dies by mint.

Alexander the Great. This finds a parallel in official Babylonian documents that were dated to the era of Philip III down to at least October 316, almost a year after the king's assassination (Bosworth 2002: 221). The overt acknowledgement of the preference of the Macedonian veterans for Philip III Arrhidaios on Series I coinage served as a statement of the alignment of Seleukos with their position during the early years of turmoil and rivalry amongst the diadochoi. No ambiguity could arise from the issuance of coinage in the name of Alexander, which might be construed as recognizing the legitimacy of the infant, half-Persian Alexander IV.

Seleukos assumed his satrapy in Babylonia in 320/19 BC. It has been inferred that shortly after this date Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A began coining in the name of Philip III Arrhidaios. However, as noted above, the coins of both mints are absent from the Demanhur hoard, whereas all but the last issue of Babylon I in the name of Philip III are present in the Demanhur hoard. Considering that the number of obverse dies used in the production of Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A Philip III issues (Fig. 4) exceeded that of Babylon I, the absence of coins from the former mints in the Demanhur hoard probably reflects a difference in the time of production relative to that of Babylon I. Consistent with this observation, Iossif and Lorber commented that with respect to the lion staters issued from Babylon II during Seleukos first satrapy, "Their lack of control linkage to contemporary Philips and Alexanders [of Babylon I] implies a change of mint administration after 319/18, perhaps the opening of a new workshop [Babylon II]."³¹

The implications are twofold. Firstly, most of the Imperial Mint (Babylon I) output in the name of Philip III occurred prior to the closure of the Demanhur hoard in 318, whereas production from Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A

³¹ Iossif and Lorber 2007: 347.

Figure 4. Babylonian Philip[III tetradrachm obverse dies.

commenced around 318 and postdates that of Babylon I. Secondly, with the establishment of Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A, coinage production at the Imperial Mint (Babylon I) essentially ceased for the balance of the first satrapy of Seleukos.

The establishment of Babylon II under the sponsorship of the satrap, perhaps initially as an adjunct to the Imperial Mint (Babylon I), gave Seleukos more influence, but not absolute control over the output of the mint, albeit still within the purview and overall administrative control of the Macedonian empire. It is probable that this was done with official sanction granted at Triparadeisos, as evidenced by the previously noted rationalization of peripheral Alexander mints after 320 and the apparent redeployment of mint workers from Arados to Babylon to initiate Babylon II. However, the establishment of Uncertain Mint 6A in close geographic proximity to Babylon, but apparently outside of the oversight and official control of the Macedonian empire is another matter altogether. This step would have given Seleukos absolute control of this mint's output and in this we glean some insight into its probable purpose—the funding of a core of Macedonian veterans and mercenaries loyal to Seleukos.

The establishment of Uncertain Mint 6A was coincident with the threat to Seleukos arising from the conflict between Eumenes of Kardia and Antigonos Monophthalmos as the theatre of war between the two moved progressively toward and through Babylonia in the period 318–316. This development was probably the motivation for the inception of the mint. Under this threat, the output of the unofficial Uncertain Mint 6A could have been directed towards the maintenance of Seleukos's personal power base and ambitions. From the outset the mint had a strong association not only with Seleukos, but also with his army, whose loyalty

its output served to secure. In this context, the basis of Antigonos's demand of Seleukos for "an account of his administration of the satrapy, and an audit of his finances"³² including a "formal account of the revenues of his satrapy"³³ becomes more meaningful. With insight into the basis of operation of Uncertain Mint 6A, it is understandable that this demand was met with a blank refusal, including the denial of Antigonos's authority by Seleukos.³⁴ Unable to defy Antigonos indefinitely, Seleukos fled Babylon to Egypt.

The flight of Seleukos resulted in the immediate closure of Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A by Antigonos. The Imperial Mint (Babylon I) was reinstated as the sole mint in the province and resumed production of coinage in the name of Alexander under the overall authority and direction of Antigonos Monophthalmos. This event was marked by the introduction the laurel wreath mint control, a symbol of Antigonos's victory over Eumenes, on the coinage of Babylon. This feature persisted on the coinage of Babylon until the final expulsion of Antigonos from the city by Seleukos in the early years of following decade.

In 312/11, Seleukos returned to Babylonia, triggering a four-year conflict with Antigonos for control of the satrapy. The record of the conflict is scant and largely reconstructed from Babylonian chronicles. However, it is clear that after Seleukos's initial success and positive reception at Babylon the city remained fiercely contested and mostly in the control of Antigonid forces for the period 310–308.³⁵ Reflecting the exigencies of a protracted conflict, in this period Babylon I maintained tetradrachm production at a high level before rapidly falling away over the next few years. Based on the start of the Seleukid Era in 312/11, Price (1991) and Houghton and Lorber (*SC*) attributed the Babylon I issues of this period to Seleukos. The historical record suggests otherwise, as does the maintenance of the victory wreath of Antigonos on the mint's coinage. With Babylon I in Antigonid control until 308, the wreathed monogram accompanied by the MI-control issues belonging to the period of the Babylonian War (Price 3745–3771) are unlikely to be Seleukid. Rather these issues probably were used to support Antigonos's campaign in Babylonia. Indirect evidence for this is found in the "Seleucus I" hoard (*CH* 10.265). Struck from 97 obverse dies, the Babylon I issues dating to the period of the war (Price 3745–3771) are completely absent from this hoard. In contrast, two specimens of the post-wreath issue (Price 3772; *CH* 10.265, 1349–1350) struck from only four dies are present in the hoard. Understandably, examples of the Antigonid war issues were not a component of the treasury of Seleukos, while subsequent issues post-dating the expulsion of Antigonos found their way into the treasury that was to become the basis of the "Seleucus I" Hoard.

³² Waterfield 2011: 107.

³³ Bosworth 2002: 212.

³⁴ Billows 1990: 106–107; Bosworth 2002: 212–213.

³⁵ Bosworth 2002: 210–245; Grainger 1990: 76–94; Billows 1990: 146–147.

Figure 5. Babylonian tetradrachm obverse dies.

With the expulsion of Antigonos from Babylonia in 308, Seleukos followed exactly the same approach to monetary output and administration that had come to prevail during his first satrapy. The output of Babylon I was reduced to negligible levels, if not completely closed, while a reestablished Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A produced volumetrically large coinages. This was coincident with Seleukos's reconstruction program in Babylonia, the start of construction of his new capital at Seleukeia on Tigris, and the preparations for the extended campaign to secure the Upper Satrapies in the period 307–304.

The monetary demand of this program of work and campaigning required new coinage. Iossif and Lorber (2007) reviewed the numismatic evidence for the substantial output of lion stateres from Babylon II required to fund construction at Seleukeia on the Tigris. They estimate that at least 75 and as many as 125 obverse dies were used in the production of this coinage, making it the equal of the combined "Alexander" output of Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A (Fig. 5), the majority of which appears to have been directed to military purposes. Like the anchor Alexanders of Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A (Series II), the lion stater issues of this period also bore the anchor insignia, illustrating the overall coherency of Seleukos's monetary program in the aftermath of the war for Babylonia.

Figure 5 and Table 10 (below) illustrate the pattern of operation of the Babylonian mints producing Alexandrine coinage prior to the establishment of Seleukeia on Tigris. This is quite different from the conventional interpretation of relatively steady coin production in Babylonia involving continuous output from the Imperial Mint (Babylon I). The latter cycled in and out of operation, displaced by Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A depending on the incumbency of Seleukos as satrap. Add to this picture the lion stater production of Babylon II documented

by Iossif and Lorber (2007) and the cyclical nature of mint operations with the ebb and flow of Seleukos's power is evidenced even more starkly.

Table 10. Chronology of Alexandrine issues: Babylonian mints 330-301.

Date	Babylon I	Babylon II	Uncertain Mint 6A
330-325	Price 3578-3593 Waggoner Group I	-	-
325-323	Price 3594-3687 Waggoner Group II	-	-
323-320	Price 3688-3696 and P178-P181 Waggoner Group III	-	-
320-318	Price P182-P202 Waggoner Groups IV-VI	-	-
318-316	Price 3697-3698 and P203-P206 Waggoner Group VII	SC Ad41-Ad43 Price 3336-3338; P138-P158 Duyrat Group V	Series I SC Ad39-Ad40 Price P159-P166 and P225-P227
316-311	Price 3700-3744 Waggoner Group VIII (wreath without MI)	-	-
311-308	Price 3745-3771 Waggoner Group VIII (wreath with MI) SC 81-85	-	-
308-304	Price 3772-3776 Waggoner Groups IX-XI	SC Ad92-Ad94 Price 3339-3359 Duyrat Group VI	Series II SC 66-67 Price 3434-3451 WSM 1240
304-301	-	SC 95 WSM 1249-1250	Series III-V SC 49, 50, 68, and 69 Price -, 817 and P167 WSM Pl. LI, A and B WSM 1241-1247 and 1332-1333

In 307, Seleukos left Babylonia on his eastern *anabasis*, a campaign that saw him absent from Babylonia until c. 304/3. Accounts of this campaign are few and fragmentary, to the extent that its substance and chronology is subject to much conjecture.³⁶ However, it is certain that Seleukos was in the East when he nominally

³⁶ Grainger 1990: 95-114.

assumed the mantle of kingship in 305. He began his return to Babylonia no earlier than 304.

Certainly after years of campaigning in the East and prior to the redeployment of the army to Asia Minor, a settlement of accounts with the soldiers would have been mandatory. It was probably to this purpose that the later coinage of Mint 6A was put, which would explain the almost exclusive presence of this coinage in finds in Asia Minor. The previously noted evidence of parallel striking at the end of Series II is consistent with the need for an appreciable volume of new coinage upon Seleukos's return from the East. It is possible that almost all of Series II was struck in a short period immediately prior to the return of Seleukos to Babylonia. In this case the entire series could conceivably date to the period 305/4–304/3.

Under the historical circumstances it is difficult to determine precisely when the decision to strike coinage in the name of the new king was made. The year 305 provides a *terminus post quem*, but Seleukos's absence in the East and remoteness from the Babylonian mints is a factor to be considered. With the exception of Ptolemy, the other Successors did not move immediately to strike coinage in their own names. The majority continued to strike issues in the name of Alexander until after the elimination of Antigonos in 301. In the Macedonian tradition the acclamation of a king was made by the assembled army, and usually then on the foundation of substantial military success and demonstrable proof of leadership. In the case of Seleukos these requirements would have been met after the conclusion of the reconquest of the Upper Satrapies and the treaty with Chandragupta. The most suitable occasion for the formal acclamation of his kingship by the assembled army would have been on his return to Babylonia accompanied by the inauguration of the newly built Seleukeia on the Tigris as his new capital. The probable date for all of this is 304/3.

Despite uncertainty as to precisely when after 305 Seleukos issued coinage in his own name, it is evident from the numismatic data that around this date he embarked on a rationalization of mint operations in Babylonia that progressively saw Babylon I, Babylon II, and Uncertain Mint 6A closed and replaced by a single facility at Seleukeia on Tigris.

Within this framework we glean some insight into the operation of the mints in Babylonia and the monetary *modus operandi* of Seleukos. During his first satrapy and again subsequent to the Babylonian War, Seleukos relied on the output of his satrapal workshop (Babylon II) and Uncertain Mint 6A, while the output of the Imperial Mint (Babylon I) was reduced to a negligible component of monetary issuance. After the assumption of kingship all three were to be consolidated within a matter of years into a single Babylonian mint, Seleukeia on the Tigris.

INTERPRETATION

Based on the combined evidence from the die study, the hoard record, and the comparative analysis of contemporary mint operations in Babylonia, the history of operation of Uncertain Mint 6A can be reconstructed and its purpose inferred. In 320, Seleukos was appointed satrap of Babylonia as a direct result of the Treaty of Triparadeisos. Around 318 he established Uncertain Mint 6A, probably at Opis, 70 kilometers north of Babylon. The production of coinage at of this mint was outside the official oversight and sanction of the administrative system of the Macedonian empire in Babylon. It was initiated using a die transferred from Arados, probably in the hands of mint workers transferred from that city, at least one of whom was engaged in the mint operation to produce the Series I coinage in the name of Philip III.

The motivation to initiate a clandestine mint operation was provided by the threat to Seleukos from the warring Antigonos and Eumenes whose respective armies were converging on Babylonia at the time. Coinage obtained from Uncertain Mint 6A was used by Seleukos to secure the loyalty of the Macedonian veterans and the small garrison army in Babylon, thereby strengthening his position no matter the outcome of the conflict between Antigonos and Eumenes. The distinctively archaizing reverse style of the coinage of this period of the mint's operation served to differentiate it from the officially sanctioned issues. The style harkened back to the earliest issues of Babylon and may have held a particular resonance for the veterans whose loyalty it served to secure.

Antigonos emerged victorious from the conflict and proceeded to purge the satraps in the east, prompting Seleukos's flight from Babylon in 316/15. Uncertain Mint 6A ceased operation with the flight of Seleukos. Antigonos asserted his authority over mint operations in the province and reinstated the Imperial Mint (Babylon I) as the sole mint in Babylonia.

Sometime after the Babylonian War of 311–308 and the complete expulsion of Antigonos and his influence from Babylonia, Seleukos reopened Uncertain Mint 6A. The output of the Imperial Mint (Babylon I) was decreased to a negligible component of the money produced in Babylonia, largely displaced by coinage from Babylon II under the direct control of the satrap. This was a natural consequence of the fragmentation of the Macedonian empire and the consequent emphasis on provincial monetary needs, military consolidation under the effectively autonomous satrap, and the construction of a new capital in the immediate vicinity of Opis. The reopening of Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A was accompanied by the placement of the anchor insignia on the output of both mints, a clear statement of the issuing authority of Seleukos. However, the archaizing reverse style of Zeus was maintained at Uncertain Mint 6A (Series II), again serving to differentiate its output, and suggesting that it had the same military purpose as that which had underpinned the production of Series I.

Based on the interpretation of the chronological significance of SC 67.5a plus that of the associated gold issue SC 66, inferred to have been struck at the time of assumption of the royal title, it appears that the bulk of Series II was struck in anticipation of the return of Seleukos's army from the east, rather than in preparation for the eastern campaign. This is consistent with the near total absence of this coinage from eastern hoards, indicating that it was struck after Seleukos departed Babylonia in 307 on his eastern *anabasis*, but prior to his return in 304/3.

The strategic and military significance of Opis was enhanced greatly in the aftermath of the Babylonian War. Located on the Royal Road, the primary route to Media and the East, it was the staging ground for the military campaign upon which Seleukos embarked in 307. For similar reasons it was the point in Babylonia to which the army would return after its eastern campaign. The reestablishment of Uncertain Mint 6A at Opis was undertaken to contribute towards the settlement of accounts at the close of the campaign. By virtue of its location and timing, Uncertain Mint 6A in this period can be considered the precursor facility to the mint at the new foundation of Seleukeia on Tigris, which, at the direction of Seleukos, grew out of Opis during his long eastern campaign.

In 304/3, Seleukos returned victorious from his eastern *anabasis* to officially inaugurate Seleukeia on the Tigris. Almost immediately he was compelled to commence preparations for war against Antigonos, which culminated in the decisive battle of Ipsos in the summer of 301. Probably at the same time, on the strength of his eastern conquests, and in accord with Macedonian tradition,³⁷ he was acclaimed king by the assembled army, either at Opis, or the immediately adjacent Seleukeia on the Tigris. Simultaneously, Seleukos asserted his complete independence, removing from coinage the possibly ambiguous anchor insignia with its potential implication of subservience to Ptolemy. He broke the last vestiges of administrative ties to the fragmented Macedonian empire by inaugurating a new mint at Seleukeia on the Tigris to replace the facility at Babylon.

In this process, Uncertain Mint 6A became linked to the army and its preparations for deployment to confront Antigonos in the West. It continued to mint coinage in the name of Alexander (Series III) for the pending campaign of the army. To this point, none of the successor kings, with the exception of Ptolemy, had issued coinage in their own name. At Uncertain Mint 6A we see the process of Seleukos's acclamation played out on the coinage. At the death of Alexander the Great, the army at Babylon had been instrumental in the succession of Philip III Arrhidaios against the wishes of the majority of the Companion cavalry and officer class. With this background, the coinage of Uncertain Mint 6A struck after 305/4 involving die-linked issues in the names of Alexander III, then Philip III, and finally Seleukos I can be seen as linking Seleukos to his predecessor kings in a numismatic statement of legitimacy. Seleukos was acclaimed king by an army at the core of

³⁷ King 2010: 383–388.

which were the remaining Macedonian veterans in Babylonia. Reflecting this and in the military context of the mint, coinage was struck apparently with view to expressing symbolically Seleukos's legitimacy as a successor of the Argeads. The die-linked coherency of this expression was a matter of design rather than mere coincidence, for the circumstance of a single die (A50) utilized to strike coinage in the name of all three rulers, Alexander III, Philip III, and Seleukos is a unique numismatic occurrence. It seems to have been the ritual practice of the mint to initiate each new phase of the mint's operation by utilizing a die from the past, a practice that also occurs in the opening of the successor mint at Seleukeia on the Tigris (cf. die-linked SC 117.7b and SC 118).

By 302 the army had departed from Opis on the long march northwest to confront Antigonos at Ipsos. The physical assets, including the inventory of dies, but apparently not the skilled personnel of Uncertain Mint 6A, accompanied the army as a supplementary mobile mint facility. This struck small volumes of coinage as and when required by the army during its deployment to Asia Minor. The resulting Series V coins were among the first, if not the first, to carry the name of Seleukos. That the majority, if not all of Series V was struck on the Ipsos campaign presages the explosion of coinage in the name of the new king in the aftermath of his decisive victory at Ipsos.

The evolution of Uncertain Mint 6A into a mobile military mint as part of the mint consolidation process in Babylonia has a later parallel in the situation outlined by Miller and Hoover (2010) whereby in 282 the resources of Seleukos's mint at Seleukeia in Pieria appear to have moved with the army to Sardes to serve as a supplementary military mint.

With the victory at Ipsos and the return of the army to Babylonia, the mint ceased operation, although a number of ephemeral, uncertain mints of Seleukos in Mesopotamia, Cappadocia, and Syria may reflect similar military mint operations at a later time. One of these, Uncertain Mint 5, dated to around 290, struck coins in a single issue (SC 61) including some from an obverse die³⁸ and a number of reverse dies (CSE 2: Nos. 25–26³⁹) that appear to have been engraved by the same engraver responsible for obverse die A55 and the accompanying distinctively-styled reverse dies of Series V (SC 50.1 and SC 50.2).

The last issues of Series V are those formerly attributed to Uncertain Mint 1 in the name of Seleukos. It is notable that there are no further die linkages to the

³⁸ SC 1.2: Pl. 3, 61.

³⁹ Note that the coin illustrated as CSE 2: Pl. II, 25 is actually CSE 1: No. 543 (SC 50.1) rather than AHNS 543 (SC 61) as described in the accompanying text on page 4 of CSE 2. This plate composition error facilitates the comparison of the similar reverse dies used to strike SC 50.1 (CSE 2: Pl. II, 25) and SC 61 (CSE 2: Pl. II, 26-27). This comparison shows that both dies originate from the same hand. AHNS 543 (SC 61) referred to in the text of CSE 2 was documented and illustrated in *Seleucid Coins* (Pl. 3, 61) and subsequently in CNG 85 (15 September 2010), lot 485.

later emissions from Uncertain Mint 1 (SC 51 to SC 54) in the name of Antiochus. Currently, these remain attributed to Uncertain Mint 1. However, the observation of a common engraver responsible for some of the late issues of Uncertain Mint 6A and the sole issue of Uncertain Mint 5 suggests the possibility that the latter may partially bridge the gap between the end of Uncertain Mint 6A Series V and the later Uncertain Mint 1 issues in the name of Antiochus. However, in the absence of direct die links this remains conjecture.

These observations leave open the possibility that many of the small emissions from various short-lived, geographically scattered uncertain mints of Seleukos and his immediate successors may represent intermittent mobile military mint operations. De Callatay has noted "Most Hellenistic coinages were produced on an intermittent basis. Mints (here the word does not even imply the use of a specific building as in Athens) were more often closed than open."⁴⁰ This is an apt description of Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia. However, when we add to this the circumstance of mobility in a military campaign, as appears to be the case in the later stage of Series V, then the specific identification, if not the definition of a "mint" takes on an added imprecision. The question remains open as to whether Uncertain Mint 6A in its final evolution as a mobile military mint found a later incarnation in some of the many other ephemeral uncertain mints of the later reign of Seleukos I Nikator and his immediate successor Antiochos I Soter.

CATALOGUE OF UNCERTAIN MINT 6A IN BABYLONIA

Obverse dies (column two) are numbered sequentially.

Reverse dies (column three) are numbered sequentially within each issue.

Coin weights (column four) are in grams.

References to ANS, London, Paris, etc. (column five), are to the major national collections, unless otherwise noted.

* in the first column denotes a coin illustrated in the plates.

All coins were struck with unadjusted dies.

Series I

Obverse: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.

Reverse: ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ on r., ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in ex., Zeus enthroned l., seated with parallel legs, holding eagle and sceptre, dotted border.

SC Ad39.1 (Price P165) ☒ on shield or boss in left field, Ɱ beneath throne.

1.*	A1	P1	16.80	London, 2002,0101.791; Hersh Coll.	A1 is die-linked to Arados (Price 3332; BM 2002,0101.759).
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⁴⁰ Callatay 2012: 41–42.

2.*	A2	P2	15.85	London, 1852,0703.1; GC30.163.	
3.*	A3	P3	16.92	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Forum, Nov. 2010, SH43277.	
4.*	A4	P4	16.48	Oxford, <i>SNG Oxford</i> 3212; <i>IGCH</i> 1795, 5.	Pasagardae Hoard I (1962).
5.*	A5	P5	17.12	CNG eAuction 97 (8 Sept. 2004), lot 27.	
6.*	A6	P6	17.03	Forum Ancient Coins, SH19441.	
7.*	A7	P7	16.86	Zlotnik 2010, 66.	Commerce "Syria" 2010 Hoard.
8.	A8	P8	17.17	CNG 61 (25 Sept. 2002), lot 486.	
9.	A8	P8	16.80	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Nemesis Numismatics (Apr. 2008), lot 7540.	
10.*	A8	P9	17.32	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Heritage (6 Jan. 2013), lot 21167; probably <i>CH</i> 10.265, one of 1287–1291.	"Seleucus I" Hoard (?).

Additional example recorded in Phacous Hoard (*IGCH* 1678).

SC Ad39.2 (Price P164) Σ in left field, $\mathfrak{A}$ beneath throne.

11.*	A9	P1	17.13	London, 2002,0101.790; Hersh Coll.	
12.*	A10	P2	17.16	London, BNK, G.206; GC30.164.	
13.	A11	P3	17.02	Noble 102 (9–11 Apr. 2013), lot 4173; VAuctions 263 (5 May 2011), lot 19.	
14.	A11	P3	15.76	Grün 62 (14 Nov. 2013), lot 59; Grün 60 (12 Nov. 2012), lot 76.	
15.*	A11	P4	17.30	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Roma e-Sale 1 (21 May 2013), lot 357.	
16.	A11	P5	17.11	Pegasi 140 (3 Aug. 2011), lot 62.	

17.	A11	P5	16.74	Romae Aeternae (Apr. 2014), lot GRP0635a.	
18.	A11	P6	16.36	Silifke, <i>CH</i> 8.308, 2074.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
19.*	A12	P7	17.19	Ponterio 152 (8 Jan. 2010), lot 5847.	

Additional examples recorded in Armenak Hoard (*IGCH* 1423), Mersin Hoard (*IGCH* 1424), plus two in Kirazli Hoard (*IGCH* 1369 = *CH* 8, 324).

SC Ad39.3 (Price P162) $\overline{\text{M}}$ in left field, R beneath throne.

20.*	A13	P1	17.14	CNG 78 (14 May 2008), lot431; MuM 11 (7 Nov. 2002), lot 623.	
21.	A13	P2	17.05	Silifke, <i>CH</i> 8.308, 2069.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
22.	A13	P3	17.22	Künker 94 (27 Sept. 2004), lot 701.	
23.	A13	P4	16.4	Palmyra Heritage 2013, lot 1755.	
24.	A13	P5	16.86	CNG eAuction 320 (12 Feb. 2014), lot 202.	
25.	A13	P6	16.61	CNG eAuction 345 (25 Feb. 2015), lot 323; Noble 64 (12–13 Jul. 2000), lot 2244; Noble 62 (17–18 Nov. 1999), lot 1878.	
26.	A13	P6	17.15	ANS 1944.100.34946; <i>WSM</i> pl. XLIII, G.	
27.	A13	P7	15.77	Ankara, Gordion I Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1406) 1 (left field monogram incorrectly described).	Gordion 1951 Hoard.
28.	A13	P8	17.27	London, 2002,0101.788; Hersh Coll.	
29.*	A14	P9	17.20	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Steven Battelle (Jul. 2013), lot U01039.	
30.	A14	P10	16.49	Eukratides Numismatics (2006), lot br142.	
31.*	A15	P11	16.73	Oxford, <i>SNG Oxford</i> 3210.	
32.	A15	P12	15.21	Ancient Imports (Mar. 2013).	

33.	A16	P13	17.18	BM 1911,0704.124; GC30.162a.	
34.	A16	P14	17.23	CNG eAuction 264 (21 Sept. 2011), lot 30.	
35.	A16	P15	17.04	Silifke, <i>CH</i> VIII, 308, 2072.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
36.	A16	P16	17.15	Künker 153 (14 Mar. 2009), lot 8251.	
37.	A16	P16	17.03	Oxford, <i>SNG Oxford</i> 3209.	
38.*	A16	P16	17.23	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Mauseus Coins (Jul. 2013), lot 00169.	
39.	A16	P17	16.10	Georg Wendel (2014), lot 21953.	
40.	A16	P18	17.23	Stack's (18 Jul. 2007), lot 429.	
41.	A17	P19	17.22	Oxford, <i>SNG Oxford</i> 3208.	
42.	A17	P20	17.00	Historia Collection hosted by Forum Ancient Coins.	
43.	A17	P21	17.24	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; CNG 341 (17 Dec. 2014), lot 238.	
44.	A17	P22	16.98	Silifke, <i>CH</i> 8.308, 2066.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
45.*	A17	P23	17.30	London, RPK,p83D.1.PhiIII; GC30.162b.	
46.	A17	P24	16.35	CNG eAuction 334 (3 Sept. 2014), lot 163.	
47.	A17	P25	17.15	London, TC,p105.3.PhiIII; GC30.162c.	

Additional example recorded in Asia Minor Hoard, 1973/4 (*CH* I, 56), three in Phacous Hoard (*IGCH* 1678).

SC Ad39.4 (Price P163) AMPHORA in left field, $\text{\textcircled{A}}$ beneath throne.

48.*	A18	P1	17.27	London, 2002,0101.789; Hersh Coll.	Die-linked to <i>SC</i> 67.1 (Cat. Nos. 75–79).
49.	A18	P2	17.08	London, 1978,0611.4; GC30.163.	
50.	A18	P2	n.r.	<i>CH</i> 8.256, 8.	Failaka Hoard.

Additional example recorded in Asia Minor Hoard, 1973/4 (*CH* I, 56).

SC Ad39.5 (Price P225-226) Λ in left field.

51.*	A19	P1	17.26	London, 2002,0101.985; Hersh Coll.	
52.	A19	P1	17.14	CNG 64 (24 Sept. 2003), lot 361.	
53.	A19	P2	17.10	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Roma e-Sale 9 (28 June 2014), lot 237.	
54.	A20	P3	16.95	Noble 77 (24–25 Nov. 2004), lot 3136.	
55.	A20	P4	17.19	Triton XIV (3 Jan. 2011), lot 350; <i>CH</i> 10.265, one of 1287–1291.	“Seleucus I” Hoard.
56.	A20	P4	17.24	Forum Ancient Coins, SH54896.	
57.*	A20	P5	17.22	London, 1845,1217.147; GC30.225.	
58.	A20	P5	16.70	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Barry P. Murphy (Mar. 2015), SKU 22924.	
59.	A20 (?)	P6 (?)	16.15	Ankara, Gordion I Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1406) 2.	Gordion 1951 Hoard. Very worn with off- center strike.

Additional examples recorded in Armenak Hoard (*IGCH* 1423) and Asia Minor Hoard, 1973/4 (*CHI*.56).

SC Ad39.6 var. (Price P227 var.) Λ in left field, two small PELLETS separated by throne strut—a precursor to SC Ad39.6 with two large PELLETS beneath throne strut.

60.	A20	P1	17.1	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Zurqieh (Oct. 2014), lot mk667.	
61.	A20	P2	16.93	Silifke, <i>CH</i> 8.308, 2065.	Meydancikkale Hoard. Low quality image—single pellet visible beneath throne strut.

SC Ad39.6 (Price P227) $\mathcal{A}$ in left field, two large PELLETS beneath throne strut.

62.*	A21	P1	17.10	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Athena Numismatics (21 Sept. 2014), SKU c1047.	
63.	A21	P1	17.09	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; CNG 814637.	
64.	A21	P1	17.31	London, 1866,1201.1122; GC30.227.	
65.	A21	P2	17.14	CNG 63 (21 May 2003), lot 198.	
66.	A21	P2	17.02	Zlotnik 2010, 64. Described as an uncertain Alexander.	Commerce "Syria" 2010 Hoard.

SC Ad39.7 (Price P159) $\mathcal{Z}$ in left field.

67.	A22	P1	15.95	London, 1939,0311.2; GC30.159.	
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SC Ad39.8 (Price P160) $\mathcal{Z}$ in left field, STAR beneath throne.

68.*	A22	P1	16.89	Triton XIV (3 Jan. 2011), lot 349; <i>CH</i> 10.265, one of 1287–1291.	"Seleucus I" Hoard.
69.	A22	P1	16.64	London, G.2495; GC30.160.	
70.	A22	P1	17.06	ANS 1944.100.34928; WSM pl. XLIII, F.	
71.	A22	P2	16.91	CNG 61 (26 Mar. 2003), lot 15.	
72.	A22	P2	16.90	CNG 73 (13 Sept. 2006), lot 427; <i>CH</i> 10.265, one of 1287–1291.	"Seleucus I" Hoard.
73.	A22	P2	17.14	London, 2002,0101.787; Hersh Coll.	

SC Ad39.9 (Price P161) K in left field, STAR beneath throne.

74.	A22	P1	16.50	London, 1880,0603.26; GC30.161.	Aleppo Hoard, 1893 (<i>IGCH</i> 1516).
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Additional example recorded from Kufit Hoard (*IGCH* 1670).

Series II

Obverse: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.

Reverse: ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ on r., ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in ex., Zeus enthroned l., seated with parallel legs, holding eagle and sceptre, dotted border, anchor flukes upward in left field.

SC 67.1 (Price 3434) Ε^p beneath throne.

75.*	A18	P1	17.25	CNG 72, 14 June 2006, 864. CH 10.265, 1279.	“Seleucus I” Hoard. Die-linked to SC Ad39.4 (Cat. Nos. 48–50).
76.	A18	P1	16.86	Silifke, CH 8.308, 2075. Houghton 1991, no. 124.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
77.	A18	P1	16.87	Paris. Houghton 1991, no. 123.	
78.	A18	P2	17.12	Silifke, CH 8.308, 2076. Houghton 1991, no. 125.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
79.	A18	P2	n.r.	Vienna. Houghton 1991, no. 126.	

SC 67.2a (Price 3435a) Α^r in inner left field, Ε^r beneath throne

80.	A23	P1	16.97	Silifke CH 8.308, 2082. Houghton 1991, no. 128.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
81.	A23	P1	16.97	Silifke CH 8.308, 2083. Houghton 1991, no. 129.	Meydancikkale Hoard.

SC 67.2b (Price 3435) Α^r in inner left field, Ε^r beneath throne.

82.*	A23	P1	17.11	London, HPB, p46.36; GC30.3435. Houghton 1991, no. 130.	
83.	A23	P1	16.88	ANS 1944.100.34962. Houghton 1991, no. 131.	Zemun (Serbia 1924) Hoard (IGCH 458).
84.	A24	P2	16.82	London, 2002,0101.793; Hersh Coll.; Sotheby's 30 (Apr. 1958) (Houghton), lot 127. Houghton 1991, no. 132.	

SC 67.3a (Price 3436) Ξ^P in inner left field, $\mathcal{A}$ beneath throne.

85.*	A24	P1	17.2	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Goldberg 84 (27–28 Jan. 2015), lot 3025.	
86.	A24	P2	16.94	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Ibercoin 18.1 (3 Dec. 2014), lot 5019.	
87.*	A25	P3	17.09	<i>CH</i> 1, p. 36–41, pl. 12–13, 8. Houghton 1991, no. 133.	Qazvin Hoard.
88.	A25	P4	17.06	Pegasi 25 (6 Nov. 2011), lot 180.	
89.	A25	P5	16.49	CNG eAuction 136 (29 Mar. 2006), lot 39; Houghton Coll. Houghton 1991, no. 134.	
90.	A25	P5	16.59	Heritage (12 Sept. 2011), lot 25928; <i>CH</i> 10.265, one of 1269–1278.	“Seleucus I” Hoard.
91.	A25	P6	15.66	ANS 1944.100.77075; WSM pl. XLIII, H. Houghton 1991, no. 135.	

SC 67.3b (Price 3440) Ξ^P in inner left field, $\mathcal{E}$ beneath throne.

92.*	A26	P1	16.93	CNG 66 (19 May 2004), lot 659.	
93.	A26	P2	17.11	Private coll., Mountain View, CA; Peus 401(3 Nov. 2010), lot 243.	
94.	A26	P2	17.24	CNG eAuction 261 (3 Aug. 2011), lot 134; Glenn W. Woods (Mar. 2009).	
95.	A26	P3	17.04	Cambridge, <i>SNG Fitzwilliam</i> VI, 516.	
96.	A26	P3	16.70	Highbating Lowprice ebay, (Oct. 2012), lot 230841556769	
97.	A26	P4	17.02	London, RPK,p80E.93. AleIII; GC30.3440. Houghton 1991, no. 136.	

98.	A26	P5	16.08	Ankara, Gordion I Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1406) 33. Houghton 1991, no. 137.	Gordion Hoard.
99.	A26	P5	17.06	ANS 1977.158.151; Kricheldorf 11 (11 Oct. 1962), lot 205. Houghton 1991, no. 138.	
100.	A26	P5	17.00	ANS 1944.100.34963. Houghton 1991, no. 139.	
101.	A26	P5	17.09	Silifke, <i>CH</i> 8.308, 2079. Houghton 1991, no. 140.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
102.	A26	P6	17.20	Silifke, <i>CH</i> 8.308, 2078. Houghton 1991, no. 141.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
103.*	A27	P7	16.82	Heidelberger Münzhandlung 61 (16–18 May 2013), lot 28; Heidelberger Münzhandlung 60 (12 Nov. 2012), lot 69; Hirsch 187 (19 Sept. 1995), lot 281.	
104.*	A28	P8	16.17	Zlotnik 2010, no. 26.	Commerce "Syria" 2010 Hoard.

SC 67.4a (Price 3443) $\square$ inner left field, $\ominus$ beneath throne

105.*	A29	P1	16.18	London, RPK,p80E.94. AleIII; GC30.3443. Houghton 1991, no. 161.	
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SC 67.4b (Price 3444) $\square$ inner left field, $\square^P$ beneath throne.

106.	A30	P1	n.r.	Hirsch (26 June 1967), lot 3120; <i>CH</i> 1, 36–41, pls. 12–13, 7. Houghton 1991, no. 145.	Qazvin Hoard.
107.*	A31	P1	16.13	VAuctions 242 (25 Feb. 2010), lot 25.	

SC 67.5a (Price 3441) E^P inner left field, beneath throne.

The presence of the control beneath the throne.

108.	A32	P1	16.40	ANS 1967.152.301; SM pl. 43, I. Houghton 1991, no. 153.	
109.	A32	P2	17.06	Israel, <i>SNG Spaer</i> 70; Qazvin 6. Houghton 1991, no. 151.	Qazvin Hoard.
110.*	A32	P3	17.06	London, 1878,0301.148; GC30.3441. Houghton 1991, no. 152.	
111.	A32	P3	16.99	CNG eAuction 79 (17 Dec. 2003), lot 44.	
112.	A32	P3	17.18	ArtCoins Roma eAuction 4 (19 Mar. 2002), lot 71.	
113.	A32	P4	17.07	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Dr. Boris Kaczynski Historische Münzen und Medaillen, MA Shop (Aug. 2014).	
114.	A33	P5	17.21	Paris. Houghton 1991, no. 154.	
115.	A33	P6	17.12	Munich. Houghton 1991, no. 155.	
116.	A33	P7	14.68	Ankara, Gordion I Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1406) 34. Houghton 1991, no. 156.	Gordion 1951 Hoard.
117.	A33	P8	16.92	Silifke, <i>CH</i> 8.308, 2077. Houghton 1991, no. 157.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
118.*	A33	P9	17.23	London, BM 2002,0101.795; Hersh coll. Houghton 1991, no. 158.	
119.	A33	P10	17.16	Peus 395 (7 May 2008), lot 135.	
120.*	A34	P11	17.16	CNG eAuction 94 (21 Jul. 2004), lot 22.	

121.*	A35	P12	17.10	CNG 72, 14 June 2006, 866; <i>CH</i> 10.265, 1281.	"Seleucus I" Hoard.
122.	A35	P13	17.12	Heritage 3026 (25 Sept. 2013), lot 26095.	
123.	A36	P14	n.r.	Superior (Abramowitz) (8 Dec. 1993), lot 504 (part of).	Entry from <i>Seleucid Coins</i> —no image available. Presence of control is doubtful.
124.	A37	P15	16.57	Auctionshaus Felzmann 147 (5 Nov. 2013), lot 57.	

SC 67.5b (Price 3438) Ξ^P inner left field, 𐎠 beneath throne.

125.	A37	P1	16.55	<i>IGCH</i> 1795, 6. Houghton 1991, no. 163.	Pasagardae Hoard I (1962).
126.	A37	P2	n.r.	U.S. commerce (Mar. 1988). Houghton 1991, no. 164.	
127.	A38	P3	16.91	Sotheby's 30 (Haughton) (Apr. 1958), lot 129. Houghton 1991, no. 165.	
128.*	A38	P4	17.04	CNG 81 (20 May 2009), lot 572.	
129.	A39	P5	17.09	Kunker 204 (12 Mar. 2012), lot 324.	
130.*	A40	P6	16.81	London, 2002,0101.794; Hersh Coll. Houghton 1991, no. 166.	
131.*	A41	P7	17.17	CNG 45 (18 Mar. 1998), lot 209.	
132.	A41	P7		Heritage (1 Nov. 2003), lot 14129.	
133.	A41	P8	16.79	CNG eAuction 269 (30 Nov. 2011), lot 149; Glen W. Woods (Mar. 2009).	
134.	A41	P9	16.73	Forum Ancient Coins, SH47736; Coincraft (London).	
135.	A41	P9	17.18	Zuzim VCoins, (2009).	

136.	A41	P9	16.02	London, 1898,0602.55; GC30.3438. Houghton 1991, no. 167.	
SC 67.5b var. (Price -) E ¹ inner left field, H beneath throne.					
137.*	A42	P1	16.28	Silifke, CH 8.308, 2081.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
138.*	A43	P2	17.22	GM 147 (7 Mar. 2006), lot 1356.	
139.*	A44	P3	17.26	CNG 72 (14 June 2006), lot 865. CH 10.265, 1282.	"Seleukos I" Hoard.
SC 67.5c (Price 3439) E ^P inner left field, K beneath throne.					
140.	A45?	P1*	17.06	Paris, De Luynes Coll. Houghton 1991, no. 169.	No image available.
141.*	A46	P2	17.07	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Pars Coins (Feb. 2011), PCW-G2848.	
142.*	A46	P3	17.34	CNG eAuction 160 (14 Mar. 2007), lot 72; CH 10.265, 1283.	"Seleucus I" Hoard.
143.	A46	P4	17.25	Peus 329 (31 Oct. 1990), lot 159.	
144.	A46	P4	16.94	CNG eAuction 343 (28 Jan. 2015), lot 230.	
145.	A46	P5	17.36	CSE 684; CNG 47 (16 Sept. 1998); NFA (18 Oct. 1990), lot 860; NFA (12 Oct. 1988), lot 374. Houghton 1991, no. 170.	
146.	A46	P6	17.18	Munz Zentrum 67, 7 Nov. 1989, 1632. Houghton 1991, no. 171.	
147.	A46	P7	15.93	Winterhur. Houghton 1991, no. 173.	
148.	A46	P8	16.78	Silifke, CH 8.308, 2080. Houghton 1991, no. 174.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
149.	A47	P9	16.79	RN 1972: 158, no. 84. Houghton 1991, no. 177.	

150.*	A47	P10	17.10	San Rafael, CA, MNL Coll.; Heritage (12 Sept. 2011), lot 25926.
151.	A47	P11	16.66	London, 1926,0701.1; GC30.3439b; Naville 10 (15 June 1925), lot 743. Houghton 1991, no. 176.
152.	A47	P12	16.20	Cambridge, <i>SNG Fitzwilliam</i> 0408_5997.
153.	A47	P13	16.98	Noble 102 (9–11 Apr. 2013), lot 4167; VAuctions 263 (5 May 2011), lot 38.
154.	A47	P14	17.08	Jerusalem, <i>SNG Spaer</i> 71.

SC 67.5c var. (Price -) No left field control engraved, K beneath throne.

155.*	A48	P1	17.05	CNG 72 (14 June 2006), lot 868; <i>CH</i> 10.265, one of 1269–1278.	“Seleucus I” Hoard.
156.	A48	P2	17.07	Heritage 18 Apr. 2011, 25079.	
157.	A48	P3	17.07	VAuctions 254, 28 Oct. 2010, 23.	

SC 67.5c (Price 3439) E^P inner left field, K beneath throne.

158.	A48	P15	16.70	London, 1911,0409.10; GC30.3439a. Houghton 1991, no. 172.	
159.	A48	P15	17.15	Munzhandlung Ritter Apr. 2013, 57231.	Die break transects A48.
160.	A48	P16	17.00	Rauch 71, 28 Apr 2003, lot 137.	Die break transects A48.
161.	A49	P17	17.06	Pars Coins inv. (Apr. 2013), PCW-G3560.	
162.	A49	P18	16.58	ANS 1944.100.34968; Houghton 1991, no. 175.	
163.	A49	P18	16.71	Lanz ebay (13 Apr. 2013), lot 230957802219.	
164.	A49	P19	16.19	<i>CH</i> 10.275, 39.	“Quetta” Hoard.

SC 67.5c var. (Price -) Left field (anchor plus monogram) erased from die, K beneath throne

165.*	A49	P1	17.16	ANS 1947.98.295. Houghton 1991, no. 178.	Anchor and control (?) erased from die.
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SC 67.6 var. (Price -) HP beneath throne.

166.*	A50	P1	17.26	London, 2002,0101.798; Hersh Coll.; Sotheby's 30 (Apr. 1958), lot 120 (Haughton). Houghton 1991, no. 190.	A50 in unworn state. No pellet is engraved on P1 die. Pellet added later, see Cat. Nos. 172-176.
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SC 67.5c (Price 3439) E^{P} inner left field, K beneath throne.

167.	A50	P19	17.28	CNG 72 (14 Jun 2006), no. 867; <i>CH</i> 10.265, 1284.	"Seleucus I" Hoard.
168.	A50	P19	17.35	Ancientart ebay (Aug. 2013), lot 390643320027.	
169.	A50	P19	16.82	Vaughn Rare Coin Gallery (2012), lot 1051.	
170.	A50	P19	16.85	UBS Numismatics 59 (27 Jan. 2004), lot 5353; Lakeview Coll.	
171.	A50	P20	17.14	Zuzim VCoins Store (2008).	

SC 67.6 (Price 3450-3451). PELLET in left field (anchor erased on last example), HP beneath throne.

172.	A50	P1	17.18	ANS 1944.100.77078; <i>WSM</i> 1240a. Houghton 1991, no. 191.	Pellet added to left field of P1 die of no. 166.
173.	A50	P1	17.14	ANS 1944.100.77079; <i>WSM</i> 1440b. Houghton 1991, no. 192.	
174.	A50	P1	16.78	Jerusalem, <i>SNG Spaer</i> 72; Peus 326 (1 Nov. 1989), lot 311. Houghton 1991, no. 193.	
175.*	A50	P1	17.30	Peus 401 (3 Nov. 2010), lot 242; <i>CH</i> 10.265, one of 1269-1278.	"Seleucus I" Hoard.

176.*	A50	P1	17.05	ANS 1944.100.77080; WSM 1240y. Houghton 1991, no. 194.	Anchor erased from reverse die.
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Series III

Obverse: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.

Reverse: ΑΛΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ on r., ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in ex., Zeus enthroned l., seated with crossed legs, holding eagle and sceptre, dotted border.

SC - (Price -) ⸥ beneath throne.

177.*	A51	P1	16.47	Zlotnik 2010, no. 11. Attributed to uncertain S. Asia Minor.	Commerce "Syria" 2010 Hoard. ⸥ control shared with Series II and V. Reverse from the same engraver as Cat. Nos. 194–201.
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SC 49.1 (Price 817 attributed to Greece) ⸚ left field, ⸘ beneath throne.

178.*	A52	P1	16.76	Silifke, CH 8.308.	Meydancikkale Hoard.
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SC 49.1 var. (Price -) ⸘ left field, ⸚ beneath throne.

179.*	A53	P1	17.05	ANS 1944.100.78126.	
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SC 49.2 (Price -) ⸙ left field, ⸛ beneath throne.

180.	A54	P1	17.02	ANS 1944.100.78128.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
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181.	A54	P1	16.85	ANS 1944.100.78127.	
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SC 49.3 (Price -) ⸘ left field, ⸛ beneath throne.

182.*	A54	P1	17.12	GM 204 (5 Mar 2012), lot 1289.	
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183.	A54	P1	16.97	ANS 1944.100.78129.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
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184.	A55	P2	17.29	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Münz Zentrum 168 (27–28 Dec. 2013), lot 101.	Dies in fresh state. Die-linked to Series V, SC 50.1 (Cat. Nos. 199–200) and SC 50.2 (Cat. Nos. 202–203).
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185.*	A55	P2	17.01	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; New York Sale XXVIII (5 Jan. 2012), lot 1036.
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Series IV

Obverse: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.

Reverse: ΦΙΛΙΠΠΟΥ on r., ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in ex., Zeus enthroned l., seated with parallel legs, holding eagle and sceptre, dotted border.

SC 68 (Price P167) ⚡ left field (recut over ⚡), eight-rayed STAR beneath throne.

186.	A50	P1	16.36	ANS 1944.100.77082; WSM 1241α.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399). P1 left field control re-cut on a die recycled from SC Ad39.8 (Price P160).
187.	A50	P1	17.06	ANS 1944.100.77083; WSM 1241β.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
188.	A50	P1	16.77	ANS 1944.100.77081; WSM 1241γ.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
189.*	A50	P1	17.1	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Goldberg 84 (27–28 Jan. 2015), lot 3028.	Undocumented component of CH 10.265 “Seleucus I” Hoard?

Series V

Obverse: Head of Herakles r. in lion skin headdress, dotted border.

Reverse: ΣΕΛΕΥΚΟΥ on r., ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in ex., Zeus enthroned l., seated with crossed legs, holding eagle and sceptre, dotted border.

Backless throne (*diphros*) is portrayed for the first time on SC 69.3 and SC 50.3–50.4. ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ legend blundered as ΒΑΣΙΛΣΩΣ on SC 69.4–69.7.

SC 69.3 (WSM 1243) ⚡ above Σ left field; eight-rayed STAR beneath throne.

190.	A50	P1	17.14	ANS 1944.100.77087; WSM 1243α.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
191.	A50	P1	16.90	ANS 1944.100.77088; WSM 1243β.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).

192.*	A50	P1	17.06	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Dorotheum (15 May 2012), 1055; Dorotheum (1949).	The throne of Zeus is backless on die P1—the first occurrence of this throne style.
SC 69.2 STAR left field, PELLET beneath throne.					
193.	A50	P1	No weight	SC 69.2 (this coin); commerce 1994.	From description in SC.
SC 69.1 (WSM 1242) H^{P} left field, M beneath throne.					
194.	A50	P1	16.50	Beirut, American University; WSM 1242 α .	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
195.*	A50	P1	17.20	ANS 1944.100.77086; WSM 1242 β .	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
196.	A50	P1	17.39	ANS 1944.100.77085; WSM 1242 γ .	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
P1 die reengraved for use on SC 50.1 (Cat. Nos. 197–201).					
SC 50.1 (WSM -) N^{r} left field, M beneath throne.					
197.*	A50	P1	16.9	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Holyland Numismatics (May 2010), lot 4065.	P1 die with reengraved control is the same as that of SC 69.1 (Cat. Nos. 194–196).
198.	A50	P1	16.86	CNG 72 (14 June 2006), lot 860; CH 10.265, 1257.	“Seleucus I” Hoard.
199.	A55	P1	16.79	CSE 1, 543. Same coin presented as CSE 2, 24 (AHNS 543)—Plate II, 24, but mismatched to description in text of CSE 2, which describes and refers to an example of SC 61.	From an Iraqi (?) Hoard. Die-linked to Series III, SC 49.3 (Cat. Nos. 184–185).
200.*	A55	P1	17.01	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Baldwin's Argentum Auction 14 (19 Nov. 2011), lot 14.	

201.	A56	P1	17.12	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Goldberg 84 (27–28 Jan. 2015), lot 3064; New York Sale XXVII (5 Jan. 2012), lot 1035.	
SC 50.2 (WSM 1332) Ν left field (incorrectly read as ΛΥ in <i>Seleucid Coins</i>), no control beneath throne.					
202.	A55	P1	17.07	ANS 67.152.669; Münzhandlung Basel VI (1939), lot 8; WSM 1332, A1 P1.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399). Die- linked to Series III, SC 49.3 (Cat. Nos. 184–185).
203.*	A55	P1	17.06	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Steve Album 19 (15–17 May 2014), lot 9; Heritage 3019 (25 Apr.–1 May 2012), lot 23176; Peus 403 (27 Apr. 2011), lot 139.	
SC 69.4 (WSM 1244) Μ left field, ANCHOR, flukes upward, erased from left field. Royal title blundered as ΒΑΣΙΛΣΩΣ.					
204.*	A57	P1	16.59	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Heritage 3015 (12 Sept. 2011), lot 25927.	A57 without wear. P1 in first state of modification. See Cat. Nos. 216–232 for subsequent states of modification.
205.	A57	P1	16.94	Jerusalem, SNG <i>Spaer</i> 75.	
206.	A57	P1	16.92	Baldwin's 52 (25 Sept. 2007), lot 69.	
207.	A57	P1	16.98	Hess 208 (Dec. 1931), lot 678; WSM 1244α.	
208.	A57	P1	n.r.	In commerce; WSM 1244β.	
209.	A57	P1	n.r.	WSM 1244γ; Ciani Vente aux prix marques 147, pl. viii.	
210.	A57	P1	16.99	ANS 1944.100.77089; WSM 1244δ.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).

211.	A57	P1	17.02	ANS 1944.100.77090; WSM 1244ε.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
212.	A57	P1	17.10	ANS 1944.100.77091; WSM 1244f.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
213.	A57	P1	16.88	ANS 1944.100.77092; WSM 1244ζ.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
214.	A57	P1	16.96	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; W. K. Raymond Coll.	Possibly the same coin as WSM 1244α.
215.	A57	P1	16.8	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; NT numismatics ebay (Mar. 2015), lot 271809597949.	Possibly the same coin as WSM 1244β.

SC 69.5 (WSM 1245) $\mathfrak{M}$ left field, ANCHOR flukes upward erased from left field, A beneath throne. Royal title blundered as ΒΑΣΙΛΣΩΣ.

216.	A50	P1	16.56	Berlin, Prokesch-Osten Coll., WSM 1245.	P1 in second state of modification after SC 69.4 (Cat Nos. 204–215).
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SC 69.6 (WSM 1246) ΑΣΤ above $\mathfrak{M}$ left field, ANCHOR flukes upward erased from left field, A beneath throne. Royal title blundered as ΒΑΣΙΛΣΩΣ.

217.	A57	P1	16.98	Naville Sale X (June 1925), lot 761; WSM 1246α.	P1 in third state of modification after SC 69.4 (Cat. Nos. 204–215) and SC 69.5 (No. 216).
218.	A57	P1	17.02	Hess 207 (Dec. 1931), lot 637; WSM 1246β.	
219.	A57	P1	16.82	London, 2002,0101.1373; Hersh Coll.; WSM 1246θ.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399)?
220.	A57	P1	16.81	ANS 1944.100.77093; WSM 1246γ.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
221.	A57	P1	16.83	ANS 1944.100.77096; WSM 1246δ.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
222.	A57	P1	16.70	ANS 1944.100.77098; WSM 1246ε.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
223.	A57	P1	16.31	ANS 1944.100.77097; WSM 1246f.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).

224.	A57	P1	16.73	Noble Numismatics 60 (21–23 April 1999), lot 1910.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
225.	A57	P1	17.19	ANS 1944.100.77095; WSM 1246ζ.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
226.	A57	P1	16.80	Baldwin's New York Sale IV (17 Jan. 2002), lot 239.	
227.	A57	P1	17.15	ANS 1944.100.77094; WSM 1246η.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
228.*	A57	P1	16.65	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Klassische Münzen (Mar. 2009), inv. no. 1151; Bayerische Vereinsbank, Munzschatze 10 (25 Nov. 1975), lot 1997.	
229.	A57	P1	16.69	Hirsch 245 (4 May 2006), lot 235.	
230.	A57	P1	16.82	Aps89herv ebay (Sept. 2013), lot 310655240092.	
231.	A57	P1	n.r.	State Historical Museum, Moscow. <i>Seleucid Coins</i> .	

SC 69.7 (WSM -) Γ engraved over erased anchor with almost completely erased prior mint controls ΑΣΤ above Μ in left field, Α beneath throne. Royal title blundered as ΒΑΣΙΛΣΩΣ

232.*	A50	P1	16.74	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Forum Ancient Coins (Sept. 2005), SH26069; CNG eAuction 122 (7 Sept. 2005), lot 59; CSE 938.	A50 in most worn state. P1 in fourth and final modified state after SC 69.4 (Cat. Nos. 204–215) and SC 69.5 (No. 216) and SC 69.6 (Cat. Nos. 217–231).
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SC 50.4 (WSM -) ΛΡ left field, ΔΙ beneath throne. Reverse dies very crudely engraved. The throne of Zeus is backless on all reverse dies.

233.*	A55	P1	15.8	Veilinghuis Eeckhout 7, 12 Nov. 2011, 39.	P1 of crude style.
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234.	A55	P2	17.01	London, 2002,0101.1386; Hersh Coll.	P2 of crude style.
235.	A55	P3	n.r.	Numismatiek ebay (11 Jan. 2013), lot 1109970364960.	P3 of crude style.
SC 50.3 (WSM 1333) Λ Y left field, Δ I beneath throne. Reverse dies P1–P6 very crudely engraved. The throne of Zeus is backless on all reverse dies.					
236.	A55	P1	16.53	CSE 2, 19; AHNS 195.	P1 of crude style, similar to Cat. Nos. 233–235.
237.	A55	P2	17.19	ANS 1944.100.78131; WSM 1333 A1–P2 α .	P2 of crude style. Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
238.	A55	P2	16.97	ANS 1944.100.78132; WSM 1333 A1–P2 β .	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
239.	A55	P3	16.98	CNG eAuction 182, 20 Feb. 2008, 80; CNG eAuction 154, 13 Dec. 2006, 87; CNG 72, 14 June 2006, 862; CH 10.265, 1258.	P3 of crude style. "Seleucus I" Hoard.
240.	A56	P3	16.82	ANS 1944.100.78133; WSM 1333 A2–P3.	Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
241.	A56	P3	17.16	Hirsch 167 (26 Sept. 1990), lot 517.	
242.	A56	P4	17.13	ANS 1944.100.78134; WSM 1333, A2 P4.	P4 of crude style. Ankara Hoard (IGCH 1399).
243.	A56	P4	17.04	Pegasi 23 (23 Nov. 2010), lot 182.	P4 of crude style.
244.	A56	P4	16.94	Zlotnik 2010, no. 74.	Commerce "Syria" Hoard.
245.*	A56	P5	17.17	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; John Jencek (May 2010), T1033.	P5 of crude style.
246.	A56	P6	17.03	ANS 1944.100.78135; WSM 1333 A2–P5.	P6 of crude style.
247.	A56	P7		Brussels.	P7 of crude style.

248.	A55	P8	16.94	CNG eAuction154, 13 Dec. 2006, 88; CNG 72, 14 June 2006, 863; <i>CH</i> 10.265, 1259.	P8 of crude style. "Seleucus I" Hoard.
249.*	A58	P9	17.07	Brisbane, LWHT Coll.; Forum Ancient Coins, Jan. 2013, SH60138.	
250.	A58	P9	17.04	ANS 67.152.670; <i>WSM</i> 1333 A3-P6.	P9 of good style in contrast to previous examples of SC 50.3. Ankara Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1399).
251.*	A58	P10	17.05	CNG 72, 14 June 2006, 861; <i>CH</i> 10.265, 1260.	"Seleucus I" Hoard. P10 of good style.

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Seleukos I Nikator's Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia